

**JUST
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T3.2 BRANDENBURG REGIONAL REPORT

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DISCLAIMER AND FORWARD

This case study about wind energy developments in Brandenburg, Germany has been produced for the Horizon Europe JustWind4All (JW4A) project as part of WP3 task 3.2. The task aims to develop an understanding of regional challenges and opportunities around wind energy governance over the past 5-10 years to formulate key recommendations to foster energy citizenship in effective and just wind energy governance regionally. It is based on a mixed method approach including for each region: document reviews (around 50), 5-10 interviews with wind energy governance actors and a media and policy analysis. A comparative analysis across cases and across the project's regions allows for a better understanding of challenges and opportunities around effective and just wind energy governance.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 COUNTRY CONTEXT

1.1.1 THE GERMAN ENERGY SYSTEM

The German energy transition (Energiewende) has been recognised as an ambitious policy objective aimed at decarbonising the economy and moving to an energy system based on renewable energy. From its inception, it was acknowledged as “one of the most ambitious national energy transition initiatives worldwide” (Moss et al., 2015, p. 1). Although the term Energiewende was first used in 1980, it was not until 2011 that it became the “official headline of the new German energy paradigm” (Fabra et al., 2015, p. 51).

As part of the energy transition, Germany’s energy system has undergone a transformation, shifting from a centralised, coal and nuclear-focused system towards more flexible and decentralised systems with an increasing share of renewable energy production (see Figure 1). Historically, the German energy system heavily relied on coal and lignite in areas such as the Rhine-Ruhr region within a centralised national energy system. The expansion of coal and lignite occurred alongside the development of nuclear power from the 1950s onwards.

Figure 1: Power production in Germany between 1990-2020 (Appunn et al., 2023)

The implementation and expansion of wind turbines were supported through R&D programmes that were introduced after the oil crises in the 1970s. Poor performance and high costs meant that deployments were limited at the time (Jacobsson & Lauber, 2006). In 1998, the liberalisation of the German electricity market was a significant milestone as it allowed for a greater diversity of energy providers and enabled organisations such as energy cooperatives to enter the market (Meister et al., 2020). This also triggered mergers and acquisitions that resulted in four big utilities: Vattenfall, RWE, E.ON, and EnBW. In the 1990s, the national Feed-In-Tariff (Einspeisevergütung (FIT)) obliged utilities to purchase renewable

electricity at 90 per cent of the retail price, making onshore wind energy economically feasible and therefore increasing its deployment. At the time, the success of German turbine manufacturers also attracted industrial policy support.

A strong anti-nuclear movement from the 1970s onwards strengthened the country's decision to phase out nuclear power, supporting the expansion of renewable energy. As part of these developments, in the early 2000s, a coalition of the Social Democratic Party (SPD) and the Alliance 90/The Greens (Bündnis 90/Die Grünen) introduced major changes in energy policies (Agora Energiewende, 2015). These included the first decision to phase out nuclear power in 2002 and the implementation of the Renewable Energy Act (Erneuerbare-Energien-Gesetz (EEG)), which guaranteed fixed payments for renewable electricity over a 20-year period.

The years 2010 and 2011 marked a milestone in the German energy transition, in particular, the Fukushima nuclear catastrophe strengthened the decision to phase out nuclear power. These years are also known as Merkel's energy transition ('Merkel's Energiewende' i.e. Angela Merkel was Germany's chancellor during these years) (Paul, 2018), including ambitious targets for renewable electricity. With the expansion of renewable energy, intermittence issues started to threaten grid stabilities and increased price volatility due to the lack of grid expansions (Geels, 2020). The federal government (Bundesregierung) started to more actively govern the expansion of wind energy by introducing a new system away from Feed-In-Tariffs (FIT) with the main objectives of codifying the determination of the values to be applied for electricity from renewable energy through competitive tenders and the precise volume control of further expansion (Quentin & Endell, 2020).

From 2021 onwards, the Social Democratic Party (SPD) has returned to power, governing in coalition with the Alliance 90/The Greens (Bündnis 90/Die Grüne) and the Free Democratic Party (FDP), and introducing measures such as the Easter Package (Osterpaket), aimed at accelerating the deployment of renewable energy, including wind energy. With the Russian invasion of Ukraine and change of government, energy policy has become a highly debated topic in Germany, including debates about who is responsible for paying for the energy transition and what types of technologies (and sometimes measures) should be supported (or not) (and with which instruments).

To sum up, Germany's Energiewende is renowned for its introduction of Feed-In-Tariffs (FIT), which have been interpreted as a means to strengthen energy democracy and public participation (Leiren & Reimer, 2018). Political and public support for the German energy transition has been considered to be strong (Wolf, 2020). Nevertheless, points of conflict, particularly in relation to wind energy have emerged over the years (Dehmer, 2013; Reusswig, Braun, Heger, et al., 2016). Recent changes to accelerate the expansion of wind energy have been put in place. Still, it is to be seen how the current energy policy changes will take hold and play out in changing (or not) the German energy system.

1.1.2 RELEVANT DEVELOPMENTS OF WIND ENERGY

Until the end of the 1980s, Germany's electricity supply system was dominated by large utilities relying on, for example, coal generation. Decentralised forms of generation were at a disadvantage. During the late 1980s, some events shaped the regulatory framework for renewable energy in Germany. The Chernobyl accident had a profound impact on public opinion and subsequently on energy policies in 1986. Between 1987 and 1990, a series of

proposals were developed, which included an Electricity Feed-in Act (StrEG) for the electricity produced from renewable sources (IRENA, 2013).

Important early policy developments of the German energy system (and wind energy) were the passing of the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) in 2000 (and its regular amendments since then), the Energy and Climate Policy Package (Klima- und Energiepaket) in 2010 and the decision to phase out nuclear energy in 2011. The package set out ambitious emission reduction targets and the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) secured a subsidy scheme to encourage the expansion of renewable energy. A two-component tariff was introduced for wind energy, with an initial fixed tariff for a period of five years, and a second period of 15 years with a tariff level modulated on local wind conditions. In addition, power utility companies were obliged to purchase renewable energy at set tariffs over a period of 20 years. The aim was to become carbon neutral by 2050 and expand renewable energy. Nevertheless, the development of wind energy capacity in Germany has not been a straightforward upward story (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Development of onshore wind energy capacity in Germany (Wehrmann, 2023)

Some have argued that several amendments to the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) in 2009, 2012, 2014 and 2017 have impacted the expansion of renewable energy, including wind energy (Müller & Morton, 2021a). The amendment of the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) in 2009 included an increase in tariffs. Moreover, grid operators were also obliged to expand and optimise the management of the grid. In 2012, a repowering bonus was introduced next to other amendments. The 2014 Renewable Energy Act (EEG) eliminated over-subsidisation, reduced assistance, and dismantled bonuses (BMWK, 2015). It was aimed at driving the market integration of renewable energy forward. The amendments in 2017 meant a change from Feed-In-Tariffs (FIT) to a competitive tendering process. Wind energy projects have had to be bid for in public auctions that have been monitored by the Federal Network Agency (Bundesnetzagentur). Leiren and Reimer (2018) have argued that these changes were prompted by pressure from the European Commission (EC) to adopt more competitive-oriented approaches and a change in the federal government in Germany.

More recently, the federal government has implemented several regulatory changes to accelerate the expansion of wind energy. One notable change is the amendment to the Renewable Energy Act (EEG 2023), which raises the expansion targets for wind and solar energy and is part of the Easter Package for renewable energy. It further categorises the operation of renewable energy plants as being “in the overarching public interest and in the interest of public security” (§2 EEG 2023), granting legal priority to renewable energy and allowing for planning and approval procedures to be speeded up (Bundesregierung, 2022). Other important parts of the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) 2023 (EEG, 2023) are:

- The expansion of the power grid and the support for offshore wind energy.
- Increase of tendering volumes for the period until 2028/2029.
- Exemption of citizens’ energy cooperatives from tendering duties.
- Encourage the financial participation of municipalities.

Furthermore, the Onshore Wind Energy Act (Wind-an-Land-Gesetz, (WaLG)), which became effective in February 2023, has been aimed at significantly expanding onshore wind energy, such as speeding up planning and approval procedures and making necessary land for wind turbines available. For instance, the act mandates that 2 percent of Germany's land area has to be designated for wind energy by 2032. The federal states (Bundesländer) can continue to decide on the minimum distance of wind turbines to settlements, but they must achieve the set targets. If this is not the case, the federal state-specific distance rules cease to apply. Moreover, the federal government has amended the Federal Nature Conservation Act (Bundesnaturschutzgesetz, BNatSchG), for instance, the government has set up uniform standards for the assessment of species protection across the federal states so that wind energy expansion can progress whilst nature conservation is preserved (Bundesregierung, 2023).

1.2 REGIONAL CONTEXT

1.2.1 BRANDENBURG, AN INTERESTING REGION TO STUDY WIND ENERGY

Brandenburg is a federal state in the northeast of Germany surrounding Berlin. The geographic proximity had led to the two federal states in parts being administratively intertwined. The capital of Brandenburg is Potsdam with 180,000 inhabitants followed by Cottbus with 100,000 inhabitants. In addition, there are about 100 smaller cities and 1,700 villages. Overall, Brandenburg is considered to be sparsely populated, seeing that 50 per cent is agricultural land (see Figure 3).

It is known to be an energy-exporting federal state – an ‘energy country’ (Energierland), seeing that it has produced more energy than it requires. The production of energy has derived from the expansion of wind energy since the 1990s but also from a long history of lignite coal mining. Lignite mining has a 150-year-long history in the region and was the primary energy source during the German Democratic Republic (Deutsche Demokratische Republik (DDR)). Lignite coal is still considered to be a bridging technology and has played a role in Brandenburg’s energy strategies. In 2008, Brandenburg adopted its Energy Strategy 2020 (Energierstrategie 2020) which was amended in 2012 and 2022. It is now called the Energy Strategy 2040 (Energierstrategie 2040).

Figure 3: The graphic shows Germany and in green the federal state of Brandenburg (Liuzzo, 2006)

The initial energy strategy set out targets for wind energy to be 7,500MW until 2020 and 10,500MW until 2030. By 2019, Brandenburg had reached 7,297MW of installed wind capacity (Müller & Morton, 2021a), regularly being part of the three leading federal states in wind energy in Germany. From 2017/2018 the expansion of wind energy slowed down in Brandenburg, which also occurred nationally.

Most of the wind turbines in Brandenburg are owned by wind companies. They have different business models but most of the profits do not stay in the region, seeing that the models are often investment-based and open for national and international investments. Moreover, the new federal states in Germany (meaning the eastern federal states that used to be part of the German Democratic Republic (DDR) were signified by mass unemployment. For years, the economy had been growing more slowly than in West Germany, leading to a widening prosperity gap. As pointed out by Interviewee 1,

“It is important to mention that the development in East and West Germany (especially in North Germany) has been very different: while in North Germany the development is strongly characterised by farming and participation, there are many citizen wind projects, especially in Schleswig-Holstein (West Germany), in East Germany it was more like the ‘Wild West’ i.e. mainly projects by third-party investors, which have dwindled acceptance” (Interviewee 1).

Over time, anti-wind initiatives started to emerge, network, and organise in Brandenburg. Motivations varied from visual reasons to nature conservation concerns, in addition to “promised tax benefits not reaching affected communities as well as grid charges impinging on individual electricity consumption bills” (Müller & Morton, 2021a, p. 6). Dissatisfaction with the planning and participation procedures, besides the locally specific issue of wind turbines in forests, has been the main reason for the rejection of the planned wind turbines. It is important to consider that conflicts have occurred not only between citizen initiatives and authorities but also between local, regional, and national authorities (Eichenhauer, 2016).

From 2018 onwards, the Brandenburg federal state government aimed to make wind energy developments more transparent whilst providing more possibilities for the residents to get involved to increase the acceptance of wind energy. Until then, the public has mainly been able to participate in formal interventions during a pre-set mandatory timeframe of publishing advanced wind plans and sometimes voice their concerns at formal hearings to approve detailed planning (Müller & Morton, 2021a). In 2019, the federal state government passed a law that obligates wind energy operators to pay a levy to all adjunct communities near wind turbines (Kerres et al., 2020). According to Mueller and Morton (2021a, p. 9), “first responses in 2019 from wind companies and citizens in Brandenburg were largely negative”.

To sum up, the region of Brandenburg is an interesting case study, seeing that Brandenburg has achieved high rates of wind energy deployment whilst this expansion has also been met with scepticism and resistance derived from organised anti-wind groups and other actors in the region (Bues, 2018).

1.2.2 REGIONAL DEMARCATION

Wind energy planning in the region is governed by the [collaborative efforts of the] joint Berlin-Brandenburg Regional Planning (Gemeinsame Landesplanung Berlin-Brandenburg) and five regional planning communities (Regionale Planungsgemeinschaften). As part of their responsibilities, the five communities develop the regional plans for wind energy i.e., they allocate areas where wind turbines could potentially be built. An additional political institution important for wind energy are the municipalities. They can look at the regional plans and respond to them.

Figure 4: The graphic shows the five collective planning communities and their area, and some of the municipalities within Brandenburg (Regionales Energiemanagement Brandenburg, 2023)

Brandenburg's wind energy planning used to be carried out through the designation of wind suitability areas that are developed by the planning communities in the form of wind plans and their suitability areas. Each of the five planning regions has a regional assembly made up of the district commissioners (Landkreise), the mayors of the non-associated towns and the mayors of municipalities. There used to be a threshold of 10,000 inhabitants for a municipality to become a member of the regional assembly but after complaints from smaller municipalities, this threshold was first lowered to 5,000 in 2019. Through an amendment of the Regional Planning and Lignite and Remediation Planning Act (RegBkPIG) in 2021, the minimum number was abolished. This change will take effect in 2024 with a maximum of up to 70 members in the regional assemblies. The regional assemblies are supported by regional planning offices. The joint Berlin-Brandenburg Regional Planning only accepts regional plans if they fulfil several requirements derived from national laws, state guidance and court rules. Such laws, guidance and rules in parts restrict the autonomy of the assembly and planning offices. Moreover, they receive their wind turbine planning targets from the federal state government (who in part gain it through the federal government).

Since the introduction of the Easter Package, planning has changed in the federal states. For instance, area targets were set for wind energy and attempts have been made to simplify planning procedures. As a result, planning through the designation of wind energy areas should only have an exclusionary effect (Ausschlusswirkung) if the area targets are met. Otherwise, wind turbines should be permitted on a privileged basis in the entire planning area. The aim has been to ensure that the required amount of land to meet wind energy targets is made available for the expansion of wind energy.

1.2.3 TEMPORAL DEMARCATION

For this case study, the research team decided that the pre-period should run between 1990 and 2018 and the focus period should concentrate on a more recent period between 2018-2023. The focus period is initially signified by the slowdown of wind energy developments in Brandenburg (and overall, in Germany) and a moratorium on wind energy in the region, demonstrating the need for political changes if wind energy was to be further expanded. This happened in 2022 with the introduction of the Easter Package. This package has set in motion several regulatory and legislative changes surrounding wind energy within the German federal states, including Brandenburg. The focus period and its phases might appear to be short. Still, this has given the research team the space to examine the currently understudied but important recent developments in wind energy in Germany and Brandenburg in greater depth. In addition, the research team has tried to provide a detailed pre-history. The start of the pre-period has been chosen because it was the time after the reunification of East and West Germany. In 1990, the Brandenburg federal state government developed the first programme to financially support renewable energy production and several wind energy installations started to emerge. The end of the pre-phase is signified by a period where the installation of wind energy started to slow down and acceptance issues were increasingly recognised.

1.2.4 INSTANCES OF PARTICIPATION

Participatory practices in wind energy are linked to a range of approaches in Brandenburg.

Citizen participation in planning and approval processes can be divided into formal processes that have been set in place by the federal government and informal processes that can be facilitated by municipalities or wind energy project developers. The selected participation examples for this report are intended to illustrate the diverse landscape of participation practices in Brandenburg and include processes that have been considered to be successful cases and where resistance to plans and projects started to emerge. Prominent examples of successful informal participation have been linked to places such as Schlalach and Uebigau-Wahrenbrück. In Schlalach, citizens formed a joint working group and implemented a land lease model that ensures a fair distribution of wind energy revenues among all residents. In Uebigau-Wahrenbrück, wind energy project developers introduced a citizen savings model, an innovative approach to improve financial participation opportunities derived from wind energy. In contrast, the case of Beelitz in the Potsdam-Mittelmark region stands for less favourable participation practices characterised by resistance to wind energy projects. Citizen initiatives mobilised and pursued legal actions against permitting decisions. For more information on these instances of participation see the text box on pages 47-49.

1.3 AIMS AND REPORT STRUCTURE

This case study traces the development of wind energy governance in Brandenburg over a time span of 33 years. It thus zooms in on participative social actions and processes for or against wind energy and outlines how these actions and processes are co-shaped by regulations, discourses and norms over time. Doing so allows us to highlight regional challenges and opportunities of wind energy governance. This report is one out of a set of seven case study reports that together will provide insights for the formulation of key recommendations to foster energy citizenship in effective and just wind energy governance regionally. It is in this way that it connects to JW4A's ambition of understanding how wind energy governance can become more just and effective.

Specifically, this report provides a historical understanding of the interplay between diverse types of actors around wind energy development in Brandenburg, Germany. At the heart of this report is an overview of the historical narrative of how wind energy governance developed in Brandenburg divided into a pre-period and a focus period. The focus period is divided into three phases: 1) Creation of the 6-Point Plan to increase the acceptance of wind energy in Brandenburg (2018-2019), 2) A transition period (2019-2022), 3) The Easter Package: Attempts to accelerate wind energy through changes in federal law (2022-2023) – see Section 4. Phase 1 and Phase 3 are connected to a critical instance of change, i.e. a point in time that was critical for the development of wind energy in Brandenburg, i.e. the introduction of the 6-Point Plan and later on, the introduction of the Easter Package. The historical narrative is followed by an 'Analysis and Discussion' section (Section 5) along the following analytical questions:

- which governance arrangements and processes are in place; that is, what was the ensemble of actors (human and non-human) that come together in the intentional coordination of social action around wind energy (for and against wind energy);
- which regulatory, normative and cultural-cognitive institutions are co-shaping social activities around wind energy (these can derive from EU, national, regional and local, for instance, planning processes and landscape governance);
- which participatory practices are being discussed and/or practised (or not) over time and how are they being perceived and implemented by diverse wind actors;

- and how are notions of energy justice and energy sovereignty being discussed, narrated and practised (or not) over time? How do they relate to changing governance arrangements and processes?

While Section 2 provides a succinct overview of the main insights of the analysis and historical narrative, Section 6 provides implications and recommendations for fostering just and effective wind energy governance in the region and beyond. For an overview of the methodology underlying this report, please see Section 3.

2 KEY INSIGHTS

The following key insights derive from carrying out the empirical work for this case study:

- Brandenburg is the second strongest wind energy federal state in Germany after Lower Saxony. Around 4,000 wind turbines with a total output of over 8,000 MW have currently been installed in the federal state (MWAE Brandenburg, 2023; Land Brandenburg, 2023). As outlined in Brandenburg's energy strategy (Energienstrategie 2040), the installation target for wind energy is 15 GW by 2040 and the provision of more than 2.2 per cent of the federal state's surface area (MWAE Brandenburg, 2022). This demonstrates that Brandenburg has had a key role in the expansion of wind energy in Germany.
- Most of the wind turbines in Brandenburg have been developed by international wind companies. They have different business models but most of the profits do not stay in the region, seeing that the models are often investment-based and open for national and international investments. This is why more recently the issue of regional value creation has been linked to wind energy in Brandenburg (and has been framed as a way to increase the acceptance of wind energy).
- Brandenburg has had several active anti-wind groups that professionalised in terms of collaborating with each other around actions against wind and developed larger network organisations beyond single groups. Since 2018, acceptance issues linked to wind energy derived from residents, communities, local businesses, and municipalities have been increasingly recognised by political actors as an issue for the expansion of wind energy in the federal state. This led to the introduction of several measures such as a moratorium on wind energy and a levy for municipalities near wind turbines so that they could financially benefit in order to increase the acceptance of wind energy and steer the speed of its expansion.
- A new federal coalition government came into power in 2021, which had the aim to accelerate the expansion of wind energy, modifying several legislations (such as the Renewable Energy Act (EEG)) and introducing new ones (such as the Onshore Wind Energy Act (WindBG)). The aim was to ease the planning and permitting process of wind energy, whilst setting ambitious targets for its expansions. Such changes have meant that federal state governments and municipalities had to face changes to their own planning and permitting processes. Measures to increase the acceptance of wind energy have also been high on the federal agenda, often based on discussing ways for residents and municipalities to financially benefit.
- The impacts of these recent changes cannot be fully grasped yet. Some municipalities still wonder how they will meet the wind energy area targets and what might happen if they do not achieve them. Some interviewees argued that planning could become easier based on the recent changes. Still, it was also pointed out that some barriers have not been addressed such as a shortage of skilled labour in permitting authorities, lengthy process times, rising raw material prices, problems with supply chains that can still slow down the pace of expansion. If targets can be met, is still to be seen. In addition, a big open question is whether the recent accelerations of wind

energy developments will be grounded in a just transition that will be carried by all and considered to be a societal project.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

JW4A makes use of a historical and embedded case study approach. The project's main interest is to understand how wind energy governance can become more just and effective. To this end, it develops historical case studies that allow for tracing the development of wind energy governance in European regions over the time span of 5-10 years. In the case studies, we focus on wind energy governance arrangements and processes and how these are co-shaped by regulations, discourses, and norms. With governance, we refer to the interplay between diverse types of actors (i.e. arrangements) that participate in the intentional coordination of social actions (i.e. processes) connected to wind energy. These can be social actions for and against wind energy.

The historical case study in Brandenburg is divided into a pre-period (1990-2018) and a focus-period (2018-2023) (see section 4). For the pre-period, we carried out a media analysis between April 2023 and June 2023. We decided to conduct the media analysis to have a historical foundation for the pre-period, seeing that it goes back to the 1990s where interviewees might find it hard to recollect certain dates and events. To be able to triangulate our findings for this period, we also conducted a document review and carried out interviews. For the focused period, we carried out a document review to inform ourselves about recent events and prepare for the interviews. The first interviews were used to determine the critical instances of change with the interviewees. In addition, we attended several online events to gain a better understanding of recent developments. The fieldwork was carried out between April 2023 and November 2023. The four methods are detailed in more depth within the following subsections.

3.1.1 DOCUMENT REVIEW

One of the initial research activities was the review of documents. We mainly relied on primary and secondary sources such as websites, journal articles, reports, and popular publications to analyse the wind energy developments in Brandenburg. Overall, 60 documents have been reviewed and analysed. The documents have been listed in the bibliography section of this case study. We used the review of the documents to a) inform ourselves about the interviewees and their initiatives and organisations, b) be able to gain a better understanding of the historical development of wind energy in Brandenburg, c) identify key events for the timeline and d), get diverse perspectives and narratives of the developments of wind energy. Interviewees made us aware of additional reports, etc. that they have written and/or found relevant during the interviews. The sampling of documents could therefore be described as a mixture of snowball, convenience, and judgement sampling.

We conducted a search in ScienceDirect with several search terms (e.g. wind energy Germany, wind energy Brandenburg, energy Brandenburg) to gain a selection of journal articles that outline different aspects of wind energy developments from the social science energy literature. As part of the case study work, we also looked at several actors, groups, and organisations websites to gain a comprehensive overview of the wind energy governance landscape in the region. Some of them have produced their own reports, statements, newspaper articles, etc. We created a database to provide a systematic overview

of relevant governance actors and institutions such as planning authorities, associations, citizens' initiatives, energy cooperatives and their publications. We chose to analyse the documents that helped us to deepen our understanding of key events and activities mentioned by the interviewees.

3.1.2 MEDIA ANALYSIS

A media analysis was carried out for the pre-period. A search was carried out on 13.04.2023 in Nexis to find newspaper articles, including the search terms: Windenergie and Brandenburg. A period between 1990 and 2018 was selected. To narrow down the search, articles in German were chosen (rather than all different languages). Overall, a total number of 1,613 articles derived from this search (including duplications). The number of articles steadily increased over time, including 59 articles between 1994-2002 and 263 articles in 2018. The articles were read and scanned for their relevance and created the structure for writing up of the pre-period. Additional documents (derived from the document review) were consulted, and internet searches were carried out to gain more in-depth information about the events described in the newspaper articles. After the media analysis was completed, a document review and in-depth interviews were carried out to triangulate the findings from the media analysis.

3.1.3 PARTICIPANT OBSERVATIONS AT EVENTS

As part of the empirical work, we have joined two online events about wind energy. The first event took place on 20.06.22 (prior to the start of JW4A) and was called 'It needs to become faster?! Expansion of renewables – What are the key issues for practitioners.' The second event took place on 30.03.23 and was called 'The energy transition in municipalities: Interlinkages between regional value creation, local acceptance and financial participation'. We took notes during these events and gained access to the slides that were presented.

3.1.4 INTERVIEWS

We conducted a total of eight in-depth interviews with one of them (interview 6) involving two participants. Before carrying out the interviews, the participant information and consent form were translated and sent to the interviewees. The interview guide set out in the JW4A case study guidelines was used to conduct the interviews for the case study. Overall, the interviews differed slightly due to the different roles, positions, and backgrounds of the interviewees. Other differences can be found in terms of the overall time spent with the interviewees; the amount of time spent on each of the themes in the interview guide as well as the use of open questions that arose during the interview. Some of the interviews had specific foci and did not include all the themes listed in the interview guide. The document review was started before the interviews and continued in parallel to conducting in-depth interviews. Most interviews lasted between 1-2 hours and were conducted by one or a team of researchers.

As an initial step for sampling the interviewees, we conducted a stakeholder mapping exercise based on the document review to gain comprehensive insights into the landscape of wind energy governance in Brandenburg. This process led to the identification of potential interviewees, including regional and local policymakers, planners, citizen initiatives, researchers, wind energy project developers, and operators. We applied the principle of diversity to ensure a representation of different positionalities with respect to the development of wind energy in the region. Interviews were scheduled based on the preferences and availability of interviewees, with some conducted in person and others

online. The final sampling encompassed eight interviews featuring two researchers with extensive knowledge of wind energy in Brandenburg, a politician from Brandenburg's federal state parliament, a Brandenburg ministry official, a regional planning expert in Brandenburg, two mayors from municipalities in Brandenburg, and two employees from an energy developer and operator. Please refer to Annex 2 for a list of interviewees.

Most of the interviews were conducted between July and September 2023. The two interviews with researchers were carried out earlier on in the case study work. In addition to capturing a research perspective on wind energy development in Brandenburg, these early interviews served the purpose of triangulating initial findings from the document review, identifying critical instances of change, and identifying additional interview partners through snowball sampling. All interviews were recorded with the consent of the interviewees and transcribed with the help of a transcription service. The first two interviews have only been summarised. During the interviews, the interviewees were told that the interview data would be treated confidentially and that they would be quoted anonymously in the case study report.

3.1.5 DESCRIPTION OF THE ANALYSIS

Following the data collection, we conducted a non-linear and iterative process of analysing the data whilst compiling the case study report. This process was signified by an interplay of going back and forth between data collection, writing up sections in the report, revisiting our data, and, on occasion, conducting additional interviews. We used deductive-inductive codes and carried out a thematic analysis. A list of deductive codes (and their descriptions) was developed by DRIFT and IÖW and sent to the JW4A team. The list was mainly used as inspiration to carry out some of the coding of the material and analysis of the collected data. Alongside the provided codes, we inductively developed codes by reviewing the documents and conducting the interviews and identified themes that emerged from them. Some of the data was coded in the qualitative software tool MAXQDR. The historical narrative in the case study report was written up by looking across the coded material. An internal review of the case studies was carried out by the Portuguese project team.

3.2 EMPIRICAL REFLECTIONS

The research was designed in accordance with the JW4A case study guidelines. As such, the empirical data collection was guided by the analytical questions outlined in the guidelines and the conceptual work. For reporting on our research, we used the JW4A regional report template developed and approved by the consortium. The use of different qualitative data collection methods (document review, media analysis, in-depth interviews, and participant observations) enabled us to gain valuable insights into wind energy developments in Brandenburg. Methodological triangulation increased the credibility and validity of the research findings.

Considering that much has happened within wind energy in Germany and Brandenburg since 1991 and the research focuses on wind energy governance (including multiple and changing practices, processes, and actors) and justice issues, there are clear limitations to the case study. The focus of the historical account (including pre-period and focus period) is based on (and partly limited by) the people that we were able to interview, the number of documents and websites we could examine and the time we had to conduct the research.

Our selection of interviewees was guided by focusing on individuals with knowledge about the (historical) developments in wind energy in Brandenburg. Nevertheless, due to time and resource reasons, some perspectives could not be included as part of the interviews such as from nature conservation organisations and citizens' initiatives. Instead, these perspectives were considered as part of the document review and media analysis.

It is also important to make the normative dimension of our research transparent, as researchers in the field, we acknowledge our normative stance towards the importance of just energy transitions, wherein wind energy plays a central role.

4 WIND ENERGY GOVERNANCE IN BRANDENBURG

Section 4 is divided into two parts, the pre-period and focus period of wind energy developments in Brandenburg. The pre-period runs between 1990-2018 and the focus period between 2018-2023. At the end of these historical descriptions, a selection of participatory practices in Brandenburg are described. The following section 4.1 describes the pre-period and is divided into several historical phases, describing the early wind energy developments in Brandenburg. It is based on a media analysis and document review and has been triangulated with the in-depth interviews.

4.1 PRE-PERIOD

1990 to 2002 - Early beginnings to boom: The start of wind energy in Brandenburg

Brandenburg, one of Germany's new federal states, is a region with a long history in wind energy that dates back to around 1990. After the reunification, the federal state government developed its first program to financially support renewable energy production. Soon after, in 1991, the first wind turbines were installed and other installations followed (Gläser, 1998).

“When onshore wind energy production started in Brandenburg in the 1990s, it did so mostly as individual construction of single wind turbines and ‘uncontrolled’ developments [...] In the beginning there was little regulation in Brandenburg as to where wind parks could be set up” (Müller & Morton, 2021b, p. 66–67).

In 1993, five regional planning communities were set up in the region that have had the responsibility to develop regional plans for wind energy. These are Prignitz-Oberhavel, Uckermark- Barnim, Havelland-Fläming, Lausitz-Spreewald and Oderland-Spree. The basis has been the Regional Planning and Lignite and Remediation Planning Act (Gesetz zur Regionalplanung und zur Braunkohle- und Sanierungsplanung (RegBkPIG)) (Overwien & Groenewald, 2015).

Initial regional plans were introduced in order to demarcate the most promising wind locations in Brandenburg (wind suitability areas), and although they established and enforced environmental protection, these considerations lagged behind the expansion of wind energy (Müller & Morton, 2021b). Promising locations have been the so-called plateaus, such as the northern, unforested Uckermark or the Nauener Platte. Between 1991 and 1997, the federal state government invested 52.5 million German mark (Deutsche Mark) into wind energy (Gläser, 1998).

“Brandenburg recognised early on the opportunities that the use of wind energy offers for the economy and the labour market as well as for environmental protection. From the very beginning, the focus was on the expansion of wind energy in this sparsely populated state” (Overwien & Groenewald, 2015).

In 1999, Brandenburg had the second-largest increase in wind energy and the largest wind park in Germany whilst comparatively witnessing the lowest level of anti-wind protests (Der Spiegel, 2000). At the time, the wind energy industry was growing with companies such as

E.DIS, EBV, Vestas Wind Energy Systems, Repower, Prokon Regenerative Energien eG and Nordex Group developing wind parks in Brandenburg. By 2002, the rapid growth rate began to raise concerns about potential shortages of designated wind energy areas assigned by the regional planning communities. Only 1.3 per cent of Brandenburg's area had been allocated for wind energy, which according to the growth rate was predicted to be taken up within two years (Berliner Zeitung, 2002).

Although wind energy potentials were recognised during this time, some wind projects faced obstacles during their development. For instance, the municipality of Spremberg initially granted a preliminary planning permit but attempted to halt the project after two years (Osberghaus, 1996). At the time, the municipality had become a municipal utility. Although they did not produce their own energy, they were able to buy it and then sell the energy to their citizens with a profit. The electricity derived from the wind park would have decreased their profits, leading the municipality to withdraw its support for the project. Even beyond this project, wind energy approval procedures were considered to be slow in Brandenburg (Gläser, 1998).

Since 1997, wind turbines became privileged projects, which meant that amendments were made to the Federal Building Code (Baugesetzbuch (BauGB)) §35 (Bunzel et al., 2019; Overwien & Groenewald, 2015). The installation of wind turbines was generally permitted in undesignated outdoor areas (Außenbereich) unless there were public interest reasons not to build the wind turbine. Regional planning communities and municipalities have been able to govern the construction of wind energy through the designation of wind energy suitability areas (Bovet, 2015; Bunzel et al., 2019). An important component for determining wind suitability areas (alongside considerations like geographical planning, wind energy decrees, political will, social acceptance, and requirements of case laws) is the Federal Nature Conservation Act (BNatSchG), a requirement derived from the European Union (EU) law.

Designation of suitable wind energy areas through planning communities regulated by planning laws: The specification of areas for wind turbines is legally controlled at the spatial planning level, with planning authorities designating concentration zones for wind turbines. Spatial planning operates within a hierarchical multi-level system, spanning from the European to the municipal level (see Figure 5). The federal government is responsible for drawing up nationwide legislations and guidelines to define planning law. Through the Spatial Planning Act (Raumordnungsgesetz (ROG)) it establishes the framework for the federal states, which, in turn, concretises this framework through state planning laws and state spatial plans. However, the implementation varies across the 16 federal states in Germany. However, it is applied differently in the 16 federal states in Germany. Berlin has a joint supra-regional planning together with Brandenburg since 1995/1996 (Bunzel et al., 2019). The Joint State Planning Department (Landesplanungsabteilung) has been part of the supreme authorities of both authorities and federal states, the Ministry for Infrastructure and State Planning of the State of Brandenburg (Ministerium für Infrastruktur und Landesplanung). It is the legal supervisory authority responsible for the approval of regional plans (Overwien & Groenewald, 2015). It also creates the state planning contract (Landesplanungsvertrag). An early draft must be published so that citizens, etc. can submit position statements (Stellungnahmen). At the regional level, the regional planning communities are responsible for the governance of wind energy through creating suitable wind energy areas. A draft version needs to also be published so that position statements can be submitted. The next level involved is the municipal urban land use planning (Kommunale Bauleitplanung). They make plans more concrete and control them through urban land use planning. They need to

inform the public early on about proposed plans and need to publish early drafts so that position statements can be submitted. Recent federal government changes have meant that some elements of the planning process have changed in Brandenburg – for more details see section 4.2.

Figure 5: The multi-level system of spatial planning in Germany (based on AEE, 2022)

In April 2000, the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) was implemented and developed by a red-green coalition consisting of the Social Democratic Party (SPD - red) and The Alliance 90/The Greens (Bündnis 90/Die Grünen – green). The act succeeded the Electricity Feed-in Act (Stromeinspeisungsgesetz) of 1990, which determined that electricity companies were obliged to feed wind energy into the grid and established a minimum remuneration (IRENA, 2013).

“After the introduction of the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) in April 2000, the numbers of newly installed wind turbines nearly doubled, up to 2,200 per year... After the “hype” of the first EEG years, the numbers of annual installations declined again, mainly due to the decreasing availability of suitable sites” (Bunzel et al., 2019, p. 18).

The Renewable Energy Act (EEG) introduced some changes to the Electricity Feed-in Act and set an ambitious target of at least doubling the share of renewable energy in total electricity consumption by 2010, resulting in significant promotion of wind energy. Instead of merely requiring grid operating companies to incorporate green electricity into their grids, the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) now mandated them to prioritise it over conventionally generated electricity. The Renewable Energy Act (EEG) further increased the statutory minimum tariffs for individual energy sources and established a nominally degressive annual reduction in tariffs for wind energy. The primary objective of the new law was to promote and finance renewable energy through a tariff.

2003 to 2011 – Wind turbines became a common sight in the region

For the first time since 1996, the number of new wind turbines built in Germany in the first quarter of 2003 was down on the previous year (Vosges, 2003). Wind energy turbines were still being built but at a slower pace. Many projects were postponed until 2004 due to financial problems and planning uncertainties. Changes to the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) and the costs of renewable energy, including wind energy were highly debated during this time. Due to the decreasing numbers of installations the wind industry started to argue for the need to keep up the subsidies for wind energy whereas some political parties argued for necessary amendments to the act and a reduction in subsidies.

From 2008 onwards, the expansion of wind energy in Brandenburg resulted in the region being awarded the 'Guiding Star Renewable Energy' (Leitstern Erneuerbare Energie) three times in a row by the Renewable Energy Agency (Agentur für Erneuerbare Energien) in 2008, 2010 and 2012 (Overwien & Groenewald, 2015). As stated by Mueller and Morton (2021b, p. 65) when travelling through Brandenburg wind turbines had become a common sight,

"Take the local train from Berlin towards the countryside – any direction will do – and you will soon see many wind turbines, sometimes less densely set up, sometimes strung together. Whether you got to the Uckermark in the north, the Nauener Platte in the west, the hill chain of Fläming in the south, or towards the Spree Forest in the south-east – the federal state of Brandenburg, enclosing Berlin, has held the *Leitstern* or "guiding star" for being Germany's state strongest in developing renewable energy three times in a row."

Since 2008, anti-wind activities became much more visible in Brandenburg, including citizen initiatives such as 'Save the Uckermark' (Rettet die Uckermark), 'storm against wind' (Sturm gegen Wind), and 'people's initiative wind turbine' (Volksinitiative Windrad), leading to actions against the perceived 'wild growth of wind turbines' (Wildwuchs von Windturbinen) and 'wind asparagus' (Windspargel) (Hornig & Dohmen, 2004). Citizen initiatives expressed concerns about "clever salesmen", "overwhelmed local politicians" and "allegedly privileged and state-supported wind industry" (Hornig & Dohmen, 2004). Activities included, for instance, collecting signatures against new wind energy in the region, networking with other groups and creating their own political parties to be able to shape local politics. As argued by one of the groups,

"We are of the opinion that our region, with almost 800 wind turbines, has made its contribution to renewable energy production in Brandenburg and we are committed to ensuring that no more wind development areas are designated and that those wind development areas that have not been built remain undeveloped" (Rettet die Uckermark (RdU), n.d.).

Discussions arose about the required distance between wind turbines and villages. At the time, the minimum required distance was between 500 and 800 meters. Some politicians argued for 1,000 meters to increase the acceptance of wind energy whereas some citizen initiatives argued for more than 1,500 meters (Taz, 2009). For example, the citizen initiative 'people's initiative wind turbine' (Volksinitiative Windrad) collected 20,000 signatures against wind energy and called for a 1,500 distance between wind turbines and villages. Moreover, changes to Brandenburg's wind energy decree (Windkrafteerlass) in 2011, meant that an alliance of 21 citizen initiatives joined forces to protest the amendment, expressing concerns that the changes could potentially remove birds from the protected species list and eliminate buffer zones around protected areas.

From 2010 onwards, some municipalities in Brandenburg began considering the introduction of taxes to regulate the growth of wind energy within the federal state and to send a political signal for greater participation by municipalities in electricity profits (Stadt Luckau being one example). The Luckau draft for a wind turbine tax provided for an annual levy of between 3,500 and 5,000 euros per wind turbine, depending on the amount of electricity generated. The additional revenue was to be used for the expansion of public facilities such as playgrounds and sports fields (Steyer, 2010). According to Interviewee 5, the tax proposal received unanimous support from wind turbine operators and investors. This way they would avoid extensive negotiations with individual local actors and would just need to contribute a portion of their revenue to a municipal fund. Nevertheless, the initiative failed because the federal state government did not grant its permission.

Next to activities and debates about how to react to the expansion of wind energy in the region, wind energy expansion developments were shaped by amendments to planning processes during this time. In 2009, a decision by the Federal Administrative Court (Bundesverwaltungsgericht) made significant changes to the planning methodology of wind energy, in which the terms 'hard' and 'soft' taboo zones were coined. The rulings had consequences for regional planning in Brandenburg, as the regional plan drafts that were already being prepared at the time now had to be aligned with the new methodological requirements. It took until 2015 for one of the regional plans to be approved while the planning processes in the other regions had not been completed due to other reasons (Overwien & Groenewald, 2015).

Issues with the creation of regional wind energy plans: Although laws had been created for the designation of wind energy, the translation of them into the practice to create regional wind energy plans was not always straightforward. This included for example, criteria for creating the boundaries between different zones where wind turbines could be built (or not) and distance rules from settlements to wind turbines. Jurisprudence granted regional planning its own room for manoeuvre to implement the laws. As a consequence plans were created that often were at risk of legal actions being taken against them (Overwien & Groenewald, 2015).

At the federal level, the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) was amended in 2009, increasing the tariffs and requiring the grid operators to expand and optimise the grid management. Moreover, in 2010 the federal government adopted the energy concept (Energiekonzept) (IRENA, 2013). The plan was to reduce the dependence on energy imports and greenhouse gas emissions through the increased use of renewable energy (Kübler, 2018).

2011-2014 Increasing issues with grid expansions, anti-wind groups and the lack of regional value creation in Brandenburg

In March 2011, the nuclear disaster in Fukushima, Japan, had a huge influence on German energy policy, including wind energy. The German federal government initiated a nuclear moratorium after the accident to carry out a safety review and cancelled the lifetime extension of nuclear energy that had just been decided in December 2010. In addition, a timeline for the gradual phase-out of nuclear energy was decided. Renewable energy including wind energy, which at the time covered almost 17 percent of Germany's electricity demand, was to play a greater role. However, Germany faced challenges with grid expansions

during this period. In 2010, wind turbines had to be taken off the grid for 107 days due to bottlenecks in the network. Problems arose because grid operators neglected the expansion of regional distribution grids in previous years. The main areas where wind turbines had to be taken off the grid were Brandenburg and Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania (Arzt, 2012).

“In 2010, the equivalent of 150 GWh of wind power was lost because grid operators had disconnected the wind turbines due to overproduction, which had increased by 69 per cent compared to 2009” (IRENA, 2013, p. 71).

Moreover, varying regional costs of grid connections and Feed-In-Tariff (FIT) of electricity generated had an impact on the level of the local grid fees. At the time, the grid fees at the transmission grid level were twice as high in Hamburg, Berlin, Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania, Brandenburg, Saxony-Anhalt, Saxony and Thuringia as in the other federal states (Schroeter, 2011). As stated by the economic minister in Brandenburg,

“This is because the costs for the distribution grids are only passed on to the prices in the federal state where the grids exist. But since East Germany is ahead in renewable energy, the entire region has higher electricity prices than most of West Germany” (Frese, 2013).

From 2012 onwards, protests were growing against new wind parks and expansions of transmission lines in Brandenburg, whilst the German federal government pushed ahead with the expansion of renewable energy, but also held on to lignite-based electricity in Brandenburg (Metzner, 2012). At the time, around 80 anti-wind civil society groups existed and were in regular contact with each other (Overwien & Groenewald, 2015). The formation of the anti-wind umbrella organisation of around 100 initiatives, ‘Save Brandenburg’ (Rettet Brandenburg) called for wind turbines to be set at least ten times their own height (10h) away from the next property and a full ban on turbines in forest areas. These demands would have effectively halted further wind turbine developments in Brandenburg (Bues, 2018).

Moreover, discussions continued about how residents, municipalities, local businesses, etc. could benefit from the expansion of wind energy, seeing that this has not really been the case so far. In 2013, a study carried out by the Institute for Ecological Economy Research (IÖW) for Greenpeace showed that it was unclear how many of the financial benefits derived from wind turbines would go to local municipalities to create a regional value. More than often wind turbines were installed without the participation of local municipalities, the municipality would therefore only receive the lease if the wind turbine was built on a public site, as well as 70 per cent of the trade tax on the operator profits. This usually was the case in Brandenburg (Nikionok-Ehrlich, 2013).

“The golden age into which many mayors thought they would lead their villages or towns with the help of wind turbines has not come. When they were told that a single wind turbine could bring them at least 10,000 euros in business tax per year, they were only too happy to believe it. In the meantime, they know that this was more of a theory. Although the investors earn many millions, they often pay their taxes elsewhere, write off high investments or use tricks to accumulate so many losses until there is no profit left to be taxed” (Neller, 2012).

In 2012, the Energy Strategy 2030 (Energiestrategie 2030) for Brandenburg was passed, which not only stipulated that the share of renewable energy should increase to 32 percent by 2030, but also that 2 percent of the usable land area should be released for wind energy (Eichenauer, 2016), demonstrating the political will to expand on wind energy. On the other

hand, during this time, regional planning offices received several thousand of positions statements mainly derived from the public that raised concerns about the wind suitability areas and to which the planning office had to provide responses, highlighting several changes that had emerged when aiming to keep expansion rates high, as the following quote highlights,

“The bottom line was that demands to triple the area for wind energy met with demands to halve the area for wind energy”(Overwien & Groenewald, 2015, p. 613).

At the federal level, in August 2014, the amendments of the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) entered into force. Some argued that it was meant to steady the expansion of renewable energy whilst at the same time being cost-efficient. The fixed Feed-In-Tariff (FIT) was replaced by the market premium for most new installations. The total remuneration that wind turbine operators receive was therefore calculated from the electricity price achieved through direct marketing plus the market premium. Due to such proposed amendments of the Renewable Energy Act (EEG), the expansion of onshore wind energy increased by 66 per cent in the first six months of 2014 compared to the same period in 2013. 2014 became a record year for wind energy, seeing that many project developers speeded up the construction of wind energy projects due to the proposed upcoming amendments of the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) away from fixed Feed-In-Tariffs (FIT).

2015 – 2018 Rate and speed of wind energy expansion are being debated and steps are being taken

In 2015, the organisation ‘Save Brandenburg’ (Rettet Brandenburg) submitted 33,000 signatures to the Brandenburg federal state parliament. The demands included the ban of the construction of wind turbines in forests and a minimum distance of the wind turbine to the next house ten times the height of the wind turbine. The submission was followed by a hearing, but the federal state parliament dismissed their demands (Gailing et al., 2019). ‘Save Brandenburg’ consequently embarked on collecting signatures for a public referendum but failed to mobilise the required 80,000 signatures, demanding that the Bavarian "10H" distance regulation should be adopted (Gailing et al., 2019).

“This regulation means a 200m tall turbine would need to be away at least 2 km from the nearest inhabited building. In a densely populated federal state like Bavaria, this strict regulation has led to a standstill of wind energy development” and could do the same in Brandenburg (Guan, 2020, p. 9).

Professionalisation of anti-wind activities in Brandenburg and Germany: Reusswig et al. (2016) have found an increasing professionalisation of the work against wind energy and grid infrastructures, due to initiatives being increasingly networked and the set-up of initiatives beyond their own cities. Social media also functions as an exchange platform for information and activities. Moreover, they have become more institutionalised, considering that individuals have become active in local politics and being elected to local and regional parliaments. Often, the aim is not against wind energy per se but overall, a critique of political energy goals. Such organisations provide argumentative tools for renewable critics, which are often intended to also educate affected citizens about wind turbines (Reusswig, Braun, Eichenauer, et al., 2016).

In 2016, Brandenburg had the third highest number of wind turbines in forested areas, amounting to 7 per cent of the total number (Bunzel et al., 2019). Brandenburg's nature conservation associations started to oppose the expansion of wind turbines in forests. They argued that the construction of access roads and wind turbines alone would cause great damage to the ecological function of forests. In addition, bats and birds hunting in the higher airspace would face risks of collision with the rotor blades of wind turbines (NABU Brandenburg & BUND Brandenburg, 2016). Debates also arose at the federal level, the federal government's goal of halting the decline of biodiversity by 2020 whilst expanding wind energy created uncertainties on how these two targets could be met alongside each other.

Moreover, at the time, the Brandenburg federal state decided to start focusing on participation and transparency issues in the future expansion of wind energy in the region (Locke, 2016) and possible ways to govern the speed and rate of expansion of wind energy due to increasing issues linked to the acceptance of wind energy in the areas. The federal state government of Brandenburg therefore supported the federal government's planned changes to the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) to control the expansion of renewable energy and considered the planned tender model to be the right way forward for wind energy. Such changes were introduced in 2017 based on amendments to the Renewable Energy Act (EEG).

Since 2017, the level of subsidisation for wind energy has been determined through tenders in Germany. This has been the most significant change to the system for subsidising electricity generation from renewable energy in Germany since the introduction of the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) in 2000. Anyone wishing to receive the market premium for a planned renewable energy project must first submit a bid to the Federal Network Agency. In their bid, the project planners specify the total remuneration they require for their planned wind turbine project. As the tendered capacities for new plants are limited, only the lowest bids have a chance of receiving the subsidy. With this paradigm shift, the federal government followed the EC's recommendation in favour of the use of auction procedures and responding to the public debate on the costs of renewable energy in Germany. According to Meya et al. (2016, p. 27), who examined the consequences of these changes,

“The switch to the EEG 2017 therefore harbours opportunities, but also many uncertainties that will need to be monitored over the next few years. If Germany is to maintain its pioneering role in the renewable energy sector, the focus on cost efficiency must not lead private and public actors to abandon their energy and climate policy ambitions.”

According to one of the interviewees, the change to the tendering system had led to “so much uncertainty in the entire renewable energy sector that at first there was a massive drop in investments, and everyone pressed the stop button” (Interviewee 6).

Next to such changes, Mueller and Morton (2021b, p. 68) citing the Expert Commission “Energy of the Future” pointed to several other challenges that marked wind energy expansion at the time such as “the increasing frequency of legal challenges to approval processes, clarification of problems surrounding protection and aircraft flight paths... and the need to strengthen the social acceptance of wind energy installations in the countryside”. These issues also apply to Brandenburg, including slow and uncertain planning and permitting processes. For example, in the region of Teltow-Fläming only every fourth application for wind turbines had been successful between 2014-2019.

Consequently, the expansion of onshore wind energy declined in the first half of 2018 by 29 per cent compared to the same period in 2017, to a gross addition of 1,626MW or 497 turbines. Moreover, it was estimated that in the next five years, 1,300 turbines (30 percent) in the federal state of Brandenburg would be 20 years old and would therefore no longer be eligible for the Feed-In-Tariff (FIT) under the Renewable Energy Act (EEG). Instead of up to 9.10 cents per kilowatt hour, operators would then only receive market prices of 3.0 to 3.5 cents. Some plants would then no longer be worthwhile to keep running due to increasing needs for repairs (Taz, 2018). Following a continuous increase since the early 2000s, newly installed onshore wind capacity in Germany started to sharply fall since 2018 (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Graphic shows: Grey line – newly built wind turbines in MW and blue graph – accumulated into MW between 2000-2021 in Brandenburg (BWE, 2021b)

This is the end of the pre-period of wind energy developments in Brandenburg. The next section describes the focus period that runs from 2018 to 2023.

4.2 FOCUS PERIOD - TIMELINE

The focus period has been divided into three phases, including two critical instances of change. The sections for the first and third phases include a run-up to the critical instance of change, a description of the critical instance of change, and an explanation of the aftermath. The second phase has been included as a ‘transition’ phase between the two instances of change phases i.e. several events occurred linked to wind energy partly in relation to the first phase and in setup of the third phase. The first phase runs between 2018 – 2019. It marked a time where the acceptance of wind energy was high on the political agenda in Brandenburg. This led to the introduction of a 6-Point Plan – the critical instance of change. The third phase runs between 2022 and 2023. A new coalition government came into power in Germany with the aim to accelerate the expansion of wind energy. This led to the introduction of the Easter Package, including changes to the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) and to the Federal Building Code (BauGB) and the introduction of the Onshore Wind Energy Act (WaLG), with far-reaching changes to planning process and targets for wind energy in the federal states, including Brandenburg.

Figure 7: Timeline of wind energy development within Brandenburg between the years of 2018-2023.

4.3 PHASE 1: CREATION OF THE 6-POINT PLAN TO INCREASE THE SOCIAL ACCEPTANCE OF WIND ENERGY IN BRANDENBURG (2018 – 2019)

In 2018, a phase of cautious reorientation regarding the expansion of wind energy in Brandenburg began. Social acceptance issues were increasingly recognised by the political parties, including the need to find ways to address them. Such acceptance issues did not only derive from residents but also municipalities, anti-wind initiatives, local businesses, etc. This led to a critical moment of change - the introduction of the 6-Point Plan (6-Punkte-Plan) by the federal state government with the following title 'Renewable energy and fair cooperation considering citizens' interests. The plan led to a series of legislative developments that shaped wind energy expansion in Brandenburg.

4.3.1 CONTEXT: DESCRIPTIONS OF THE SITUATION IN BRANDENBURG BEFORE THE INTRODUCTION OF THE 6-POINT PLAN

In 2018, several elements influenced the development of wind energy in Brandenburg. This included: a) the diminishing commitment of the federal government towards the German energy transition, b) the accumulation of reasons for the decreasing acceptance of wind energy in Brandenburg, c) the political situation in Brandenburg in which such acceptance issues arose, d) actions against regional wind energy plans that one by one were made invalid by the courts, and e) increasing reservations against wind energy by some municipalities in the region. These points are illustrated one by one in more detail below.

Uncertainties in wind energy due to the federal government's hesitant commitment towards the German energy transitions

For a considerable time, Germany was hailed as a trailblazer in the realm of renewable energy expansion, consistently advocating for more ambitious objectives at the EU level. However, in mid-2018, the Federal Minister for Economic Affairs and Energy (Bundesminister für Wirtschaft und Energie), Peter Altmaier, took a different stance. He opposed an EU directive seeking to achieve a 35 per cent share of total energy consumption from renewable sources by 2030 (although, it had already been approved by the European Parliament (EP)). Peter Altmaier stressed that his concerns were not against renewable energy in general, but about the affordability and feasibility of these technologies. He also highlighted the risk of eroding public trust in politics if unattainable goals were set that then would remain unfulfilled. Peter Altmaier deemed the 35 per cent renewable energy target for 2030 as unattainable, considering that despite Germany's consistent efforts only 15 per cent share had been achieved (Reimer & Rößler, 2023). This situation raised questions about the federal government's commitment to seriously continue the pursuit of the German energy transition (Interviewees 1 and 6). Such perceived lack of commitment led to a situation where the wind energy sector and federal state governments were increasingly uncertain about the future role of wind energy in the German regions, including Brandenburg, which had seen itself as a pioneer in wind energy.

Wind energy acceptance issues in Brandenburg

Acceptance issues linked to wind energy were increasingly recognised as a hindrance to wind energy developments in Brandenburg throughout 2018. Ways to address such issues therefore became an important point on the regional political agenda. Such acceptance issues have been based on several issues:

- **Who carries the financial burden of the expansion of wind energy?** Brandenburg has often had one of the highest electricity prices in Germany due to increasing network charges (Netzentgelte) for expanding the grid. Such charges have varied enormously across the German federal states. In 2018, "according to the Federal Network Agency, grid fees alone often amount to 7.25 cents per kilowatt hour in Brandenburg. In large parts of western Germany, consumers pay significantly less" (Hackenbruch, 2018). This was also pointed out by one of the interviewees,

"It's a paradox because renewable sources produce cheap electricity. However, to connect these installations, you need to lay power lines everywhere, and the finance for this expansion isn't distributed nationwide but rather regionally. The fact that this is unfair is a widely held awareness. People know it's the case and consider it unfair" (Interviewee 6).

- **Who benefits from the expansion of wind energy?** In East Germany, most wind parks have been built and operated by big international investors and energy companies with no legal obligations to offer any kind of financial participation to residents or municipalities. Based on these experiences, the economic value of expanding renewable energy had consequently been increasingly questioned by residents, municipalities, and other political stakeholders (Interviews 4, 5, 7, 8). The experience of unfairness has been exacerbated by the lack of regional value creation based on wind energy.

- **Who can decide where wind energy can be built i.e. regional plans for wind energy?**
Another point of conflict in 2018 was the limited involvement of small municipalities in the decision-making process concerning the creation of regional plans for wind energy. The regional assemblies serve as the central decision-making bodies for regional planning of wind energy. They are comprised of mayors and district administrators, representing municipalities in the respective planning areas. In 2018, a population threshold of 10,000 residents was established as the minimum requirement for an appointment to the regional assembly in Brandenburg. Municipalities with fewer residents could take part in discussions and express their concerns, but they lacked the voting rights necessary for being included in the final decisions. An interviewee described the situation as followed,

"There were municipalities or districts with a large area that typically don't have ten thousand residents. They were all excluded from participating in the decision-making process for regional planning. In a democratic sense, they couldn't contribute to the decision-making process. While they were involved in the administrative process and had a chance to voice their opinions, the opportunity to propose changes or engage in more active participation was not available. I must emphasise that this was a significant shortcoming in the past" (Interviewee 5).

One of the interviewees shared a similar view,

"This was a matter of great concern for some municipalities because they felt excluded and, as a result, had no say in regional planning. They were left out of the process. [...] The main argument made by these smaller municipalities for wanting representation in the regional assembly was that wind energy expansion was happening right in their local area. They were the ones who are directly impacted by the regional plans but were not allowed to participate in the decision-making process. This was their key argument" (Interviewee 3).

Increasing recognition of wind energy acceptance issues before the federal state and municipal elections

In 2018, the pre-election campaign for the upcoming federal state and municipal elections kicked off in Brandenburg. Acceptance issues therefore became a key issue in the political pre-election discourse,

"In order to continue the federal state's energy policy path, the energy transition must be supported by broad sections of the population, and the concerns of individuals must be taken seriously" (Uwe Steffen, Deputy Head of Department at the Ministry of Economy and Energy of the State of Brandenburg (Stellvertretender Abteilungsleiter im Ministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie des Landes Brandenburg) (Steffen, 2019).

Additionally, the high recognition of acceptance issues was compounded by the strong polling numbers of the Alternative for Germany (Alternative für Deutschland, (AfD)), a right-wing populist political party in Germany that has an anti-wind stance, as explained by one of the interviewees,

"During that time, it seemed like the AfD might gain around forty per cent or more, and they [the other parties] had to find ways to counter such increases in their election campaigns" (Interviewee 6).

One way to do so was to find ways to address wind energy acceptance issues or at least being seen to do so.

Regional plans were made invalid in court cases, creating an uncertain legal situation for wind energy

Following numerous complaints from a coalition of actors (including, for example, the wind energy sector, owners of land, and municipalities), the Higher Administrative Court (Oberlandesgericht) of Berlin-Brandenburg declared the 'Havelland-Fläming 2020' regional plan invalid due to formal errors in 2018. The prosecutors had objected to the designation of areas for wind energy in the regional plan. The court decided that contrary to the legal mandate, insufficient space had been created for wind energy. Over the following years, several court cases against other regional plans emerged, also making them invalid within court cases often due to formal errors. For example, in Oberland-Spree a court ruling occurred in 2021. Two municipalities in the region had filed a lawsuit. A landowner, who lives approximately 800 metres away from a designated wind suitability area had filed an additional review of the plan. A fourth applicant filed a complaint based on what was perceived as insufficient consideration of repowering interests. Like the Uckermark-Barnim regional plan, which the senate declared invalid in the spring of 2021, in Oberland-Spree deficiencies in the announcement of the public consultation alone rendered the regional plan invalid. The lack of legal regional plans created uncertainties for the wind energy sector in Brandenburg that put into question Brandenburg's commitment towards wind energy as the planning for wind energy was perceived to become less certain and riskier (BWE, 2021a). The absence of valid regional plans meant that there were no exclusion areas for wind energy.

Increasing reservations towards wind energy at the municipal level

In June 2018, the mayors from the municipalities of Ahrensfelde, Wandlitz and the town of Bernau signed the Bernau declaration (Bernauer Erklärung) together with 23 mayors from other municipalities. The declaration outlined, for example, the requirement not to build wind turbines in forests and ensure a minimum distance of 1,500m from settlements (Bündnis für Bernau, 2018; Walker, 2022). Afterwards, this declaration was sent to all majors across the federal state to make it a Brandenburg declaration, demonstrating that the acceptance of wind energy was not only influenced by residents, local businesses, and anti-wind groups but also municipalities in the regions. In the end, the Bernau Declaration turned into the Brandenburg Declaration, signed by 270 local leaders, and submitted to the State Parliament's President in May 2018, approximately one year after the Bernau Declaration but featuring the same content (Pankower Allgemeine Zeitung, 2019).

In addition, some municipalities started to file lawsuits against regional plans (see section above). According to one of the interviewees, such lawsuits can be explained due to some municipalities holding the belief that the aim of regional planning had been to allocate as much land as possible for wind energy. This was not the case,

"The impact of regional planning was to confine wind energy projects to designated suitability areas. Outside of these areas, the use of wind energy was essentially restricted, if not outright prohibited. The objective was to allocate only about 2 percent of the regional land for wind energy installations, keeping approximately 98 per cent of the regional

territory free from such developments, especially new wind energy projects. Regrettably, this aspect of regional planning was not fully understood" (Interviewee 3).

According to the interviewee, the consequences of such lawsuits – no regional plans meaning no exclusion areas for wind energy – were sometimes not adequately considered by the municipalities and other prosecutors. For these actors, the results of such lawsuits could therefore have some unintended consequences,

"This is not what we intended. [...] It only became apparent when a regional plan was invalidated that it could potentially cause harm" (Interviewee 3).

4.3.2 CRITICAL INSTANCE OF CHANGE: INTRODUCTION OF THE 6-POINT PLAN IN BRANDENBURG

Due to the increasing recognition of the need to address acceptance issues, the federal state government wanted to create opportunities for citizens and municipalities to participate financially in the energy transitions to increase the regional value creation based on wind energy. This recognition resulted in a cabinet decision to introduce the 6-Point Plan with the aim of achieving more of a balance between existing energy policy goals and the interests of citizens, etc. in September 2018 (Steffen, 2019). The following points were mentioned in the plan:

1. A special levy for municipalities near to wind turbines,
2. An improvement of advisory services for renewable energy,
3. An increased use of compensation payments for municipal projects,
4. Needs-based night-time labelling of wind turbines,
5. Safeguarding of regional planning, and
6. Strengthening of municipal planning sovereignty.

Some points in the 6-Point Plan sparked debates between actors. For instance, the wind energy sector was worried about the introduction of point 5. This point was aimed at, for example, a) the prevention of the 'uncontrolled' construction of wind turbines outside of wind suitability areas and b) the prohibition of authorisations of wind energy in regions where the regional plan had become invalid, preventing 'uncontrolled growth' during the period when new regional plans had to be drawn up by the planning communities (Steffen, 2019). One of the interviewees described the situation as followed,

"The government wanted to basically freeze everything and first evaluate what should still be possible and what should no longer be possible. They said, well, we've already anchored eight gigawatts in our targets and we're making good progress. We're already doing quite a lot. Everyone else should start doing something now too. So, let's hit the brakes for now" (Interviewee 6).

In the end, not all proposed measures were put into practice. It also is unclear whether the plan's aim to achieve greater acceptance of wind energy in the region has been successful, considering that major federal changes to wind energy regulation were introduced in 2022 and not enough time had passed to determine the influence of the plan before the changes came in.

4.3.3 DEVELOPMENTS OF WIND ENERGY AFTER THE INTRODUCTION OF THE 6-POINT PLAN

Several measures linked to the plan were introduced over the coming year and shaped the development of wind energy in the region. Some of the key changes are described below and have included: a) the introduction of a moratorium on wind energy in the region, b) increasing opportunities for smaller municipalities to participate in decision-making processes around the development of regional wind energy plans in regional assemblies, c) establishment of a special levy for municipalities close to the wind turbines, d) a new advisory service for wind energy, and e) an attempt to strengthen the decision-making power of municipalities within wind energy.

Introduction of a moratorium on wind energy in Brandenburg

On 1 May 2019, a so-called wind energy moratorium came into force in the federal state of Brandenburg based on an amendment to the Regional Planning and Lignite and Remediation Planning Act (RegBkPIG) also known as the regional planning act. The moratorium had serious consequences for the planning regions whose regional plans for wind energy had proven to be invalid according to the case law of the Berlin-Brandenburg Higher Administrative Court. The authorisation of wind turbines was no longer permitted in these planning regions for an initial period of two years (BWE, 2019). The regional planning authority was also required to promptly initiate the process of creating and updating the regional plan.

“The federal state responded by saying: Well, it takes some time to redevelop a regional plan, and during this transitional period, we will implement a kind of protective shield, the so-called moratorium. It was established in 2019 to prevent the widespread use of wind energy during the redevelopment of the regional plans” (Interviewee 3).

At the time, this included two planning regions Havelland-Fläming and Lausitz Spreewald. Over the years more regional plans were declared to be invalid, demonstrating the increasing impact of the moratorium. The wind industry, particularly wind energy developers, were worried that such changes would significantly hinder the expansion of wind energy in Brandenburg. In response to the draft law, the state association of the German Wind Energy Association (Bundesverband WindEnergie e.V., (BWE)) asked for several exemptions that would allow for a continued wind energy expansion despite the moratorium. Some of these exemptions were ultimately included in the adopted law. To prevent a sudden halt of wind energy, they ensured that projects that were already well advanced at the time of the moratorium would not be affected (KNE, 2019).

Increasing opportunities for smaller municipalities to participate in the development of regional plans

Changes to the regional planning act also allowed for smaller self-governing municipalities and municipal associations (Ämter and Verbandsgemeinden) with a minimum population of 5,000 residents to be represented in the regional assembly (Regionalversammlung) where regional plans could be updated, modified and, if necessary, revoked. Previously, only municipalities with over 10,000 residents were able to make such decisions about the regional plans, allowing smaller municipalities to have their say on the development of wind energy. The federal state government's official rationale for this change was to better harness local expertise in the decision-making process of regional planning procedures (KNE, 2019).

"At that time, the government addressed the concerns of smaller municipalities and stated, 'we want to include them in the regional assembly, giving them the opportunity not only to voice their opinions but also to make decisions'. This led to a change in state law. As a result, regional assemblies became significantly larger, with up to 60 members instead of 45. This means that decision-making now involves a greater number of members, which isn't always easier. More members naturally bring more questions and, logically, perhaps more diverse interests" (Interviewee 3).

Such changes increased the number of eligible regional council members in each region, raising the maximum number to 60 members within the regional assembly. Concerns regarding the expansion of regional assemblies mainly revolved around the potential for debates to become more complex and contentious. Finding compromises and building majorities could become more challenging (Interviewee 3).

Introducing a special levy for municipalities close to the wind turbines

On June 19, 2019, the Brandenburg federal state parliament passed the Wind Turbine Levy Law (Windenergieanlagenabgabegesetz, BbgWindAbgG), a law that introduced a special levy for wind turbines for municipalities close to them. According to this law, wind energy operators with wind turbines commissioned after December 31, 2019, were obligated to make annual payments of 10,000 euros to the municipalities located within a three-kilometre radius of the wind turbines. If multiple municipalities fall within this radius, the payment would be distributed proportionally based on the size of the affected municipal areas. The decision to include neighbouring municipalities within a three-kilometre radius was a compromise between the proposal put forth by the Christian Democratic Union (CDU) to involve municipalities within a five-kilometre radius of wind turbines and the proposal by the Social Democratic Party and The Left party (SPD and Die Linke) to only involve the 'host' municipality (Zerzawy et al., 2023).

The revenues generated from this special levy are meant to be earmarked for specific projects and not become part of the municipal financial equalisation system, which is a mechanism for balancing the financial capacity of municipalities within a federal state. Therefore, eligible municipalities are meant to benefit fully from the generated revenues. Such funds are meant to be used for initiatives that enhance the acceptance of wind energy. Residents should be able to see a direct link between the levy payments from wind energy and projects financed in the municipality. Potential measures include:

- Improving the local appearance and locally bound infrastructure.
- Providing information about electricity generation from renewable energy and their potential uses.
- Supporting events, social activities, cultural, educational, and recreational facilities, or entrepreneurial activities in the municipality.
- Engaging in municipal land-use planning in the field of renewable energy.

Discussions about such a levy had already been held at the federal level but it was decided not to wait for a federal government decision and just introduce the levy at the federal state level. Other federal states such as Mecklenburg-Vorpommern had already done so. It was not until October 2019 that the federal government, through the Climate Action Programme 2030 (Klimaschutzprogramm 2030), decided to make the necessary legislative adjustments to involve municipalities financially in the operation of wind turbines. Such adjustments were to be regulated through an amendment to the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) in 2020, although it ultimately took until 2021 to come into effect. The impacts of both legislative measures on the acceptance of wind energy are still unclear, but one of the interviewees said,

“And I have the impression that it's getting there - bit by bit - in one community or another. You sometimes read articles in the press where it says that municipality XY is discussing a wind park in its local council and everyone used to be against it, and now you realise, oh, it could be worthwhile, maybe we're in favour of it now after all. There are these examples. But I can't tell you in how many cases this has already happened in Brandenburg. There are also other municipalities where the possibility hasn't even arrived yet. So, there was another report this week. I think it was on RBB [Rundfunk Berlin-Brandenburg, regional radio station] actually, where one municipality still said, we want to get something out of it and we can't, and so that it obviously hasn't sunk in yet that you actually get something for it” (Interviewee 3).

New advisory services for renewable energy

The 6-Point Plan also outlined the need to improve advisory services for renewable energy in Brandenburg. As a result, in January 2019, a new advisory service was established by the Economic Development Agency in Brandenburg (Wirtschaftsförderung Brandenburg, (WFBB)), which has already functioned as the federal state's energy agency. To be able to create a service that does not only enhance the acceptance of wind energy in the region through providing advice, but also by mediating and facilitating interactions between investors, municipalities, and citizens, WFBB joined forces with the Competence Centre for Nature Conservation and Energy Transition (Kompetenzzentrum für Naturschutz und Energiewende (KNE)).

"The new service particularly focuses on the planning process for wind energy, specifically on the role of municipalities in designating areas for wind and solar parks. It also provides information about financial participation opportunities for citizens and municipalities in specific renewable energy projects, along with assessing their economic viability. We also offer support for municipal projects involving renewable energy installations. In instances of conflicts, we collaborate with the Competence Centre for Nature Conservation and Energy Transition, which provides on-site moderation and mediation possibilities" (MWAE Brandenburg, 2019).

In the initial phase, the Brandenburg Ministry of Economy and Energy (Ministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie des Landes Brandenburg), in partnership with the Economic Development Agency Brandenburg (Wirtschaftsförderungsgesellschaft Brandenburg, (WFBB)) and the Agency for Renewable Energies (Agentur für Erneuerbare Energien (AEE)), organised regional conferences under the following title 'New opportunities for municipalities and municipal utilities (Stadtwerke) through acceptance measures in renewable energy' (Neue Chancen für Kommunen und Stadtwerke durch aktuelle Akzeptanzmaßnahmen bei den erneuerbaren Energien) in each of the five planning regions. The purpose of these conferences was to discuss the proposed measures outlined in the 6-Point Plan. Furthermore, they aimed to develop opportunities for municipalities to participate actively in the development of wind energy (MWAE Brandenburg, 2018).

Attempting to strengthen the decision-making power of municipalities within wind energy

As an additional component of the 6-Point Plan, Minister President (Ministerpräsident) Dietmar Woidke introduced an initiative to grant municipalities greater decision-making powers within wind energy developments to the federal council (Bundesrat), the legislative body representing Germany's sixteen federal states at the federal level (Süddeutsche Zeitung, 2018) specifically aimed to remove the existing privilege for wind turbines within the Federal Building Code (BauGB). As part of the existing law, the installation of wind turbines would be permitted as so-called privileged projects if there was no public interest that would oppose it. By removing the privilege, a wind turbine would only be able to be installed if the local municipality agreed to it.

The Association of Cities and Municipalities (Städte- und Gemeindebund) in Brandenburg and others had long called for changes in the Federal Building Code (BauGB), arguing that, in practice, municipalities did not possess a veto right in construction decisions. Strengthening their role in the decision-making process was seen as necessary to foster local acceptance towards wind energy. Frustration had grown, particularly among smaller municipalities that felt that wind parks were being built in areas with fewer than 10,000 inhabitants without their input (Höppner & Anker, 2019). The German Wind Energy Association (BWE) was worried about the proposed initiative, describing the removal of the wind energy privilege as "effectively stalling wind energy expansion" (BWE, 2018).

During a speech to the federal council (Bundesrat), Dietmar Woidke acknowledged the burdens faced by residents near wind parks, reducing the acceptance of wind energy. Dietmar Woidke emphasised that the goal of the initiative was to democratise the decision-making process linked to wind energy, rather than weaken its development in Germany (Staatskanzlei Brandenburg, 2018). Despite the initial efforts, the initiative ultimately failed in the federal council.

To sum up, wind energy acceptance issues have been increasingly politically recognised in Brandenburg since 2018. This led to the introduction of the 6-Point Plan, with the aim to be able to govern the speed and rate of expansion and increase the acceptance within the municipalities and their residents.

4.4 PHASE 2: A TRANSITION PERIOD BETWEEN THE TWO CRITICAL INSTANCES OF CHANGE (2019 – 2021)

After the federal state election in September 2019, a new coalition government (Social Democratic Party of Germany (SPD) and Christian Democratic Union of Germany (CDU)) was formed in Brandenburg, with Minister President (Ministerpräsident) Dietmar Woidke continuing to lead as a minister president the federal state. In the coalition agreement, the federal state government committed to the existing goal of expanding wind energy capacity to 10,500 MW by 2030. The primary objective of increasing the acceptance of wind energy remained high on the agenda. The coalition government stressed the importance of ensuring that the financial benefits derived from renewable energy expansions stay within the affected areas. Additionally, they expressed their intention to involve the impacted municipalities more in the planning process (SPD Brandenburg et al., 2019).

In addition, in 2020, the new coalition government introduced its aim to move towards a climate-neutral Brandenburg as a policy goal for the first time. The process of crafting a climate plan (Klimaplan) for Brandenburg started in June 2020. The Brandenburg federal state parliament issued a directive to the federal state government, instructing them to create a comprehensive climate plan to address the challenges posed by global warming. The plan was expected to include a binding climate strategy and a set of measures to combat climate change, including ambitious expansion targets for wind energy. Furthermore, the resolution called for the introduction of a climate assessment mechanism. The development of the climate plan did not commence until after 2021, and as of now, the decision-making process about the plan remains incomplete (RBB24, 2020) (see phase 3 of the focus period for additional details).

After the election and into 2020, wind energy developments slowed down. One factor that played a role was the global COVID-19 pandemic, which took up a significant number of financial and professional resources in the German federal states for an extended period. In addition, another significant factor was the decision by the federal government to phase out coal-fired power generation in 2020, a topic that had been under discussion for several years. Brandenburg, with its significant lignite reserves, had to navigate the challenge of crafting a new 'energy narrative' in a region with a deep-rooted cultural history associated with lignite (Interviewee 7). The attention of policymakers shifted towards implementing the legislative changes, including the Coal Exit Act (Kohleausstiegsgesetz) and the Structural Reinforcement Act for Mining Regions (Strukturstärkungsgesetz), which led to wind energy, at least temporarily, not being the main focus of policy-making.

On June 16, 2021, the Brandenburg state parliament approved the second amendment to the Regional Planning and Lignite and Remediation Planning Act (RegBkPIG). The primary focus of the new legislation was the extension of the wind energy moratorium. The prohibition about building wind turbines in areas where the regional plans for wind energy had been invalidated by the Higher Administrative Court remained in place to facilitate the preparation of new regional plans. The initial moratorium was set for two years, and with the new amendment, it could be extended twice for an additional year each time. This extension became necessary because none of the regional planning communities in Brandenburg were able to develop new regional plans within the original time frame, primarily due to the constraints imposed by the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic (Maltschew, 2021).

In March 2021, the federal state government already announced that the expansion targets for wind energy in Brandenburg for 2023 would be missed. Nonetheless, there was a slight increase in wind energy installation in 2020 (242MW) and 2021 (413MW).

At the federal level, one key event during this phase was the amendment of the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) in 2020. This was due to the recognition of growing conflicts regarding the acceptance of wind energy. The amendment, which took effect on January 1, 2021, aimed to enhance financial participation and boost tax revenues for municipalities near wind turbines. This step was part of the federal government's broader effort to engage municipalities financially in wind turbine operations to improve local acceptance, as previously outlined in the Climate Protection Program 2030 (Klimaschutzprogramm 2030) at the end of 2019. In May 2020, the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Energy (Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie) presented a concept paper for a regulatory proposal, allowing both municipalities and residents to financially partake in the earnings generated by new wind energy parks supported by the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) from 2021 onwards. However, the final legislation only included financial participation for municipalities. Specifically, §6 EEG 2021 introduced the option for municipalities to financially participate while limiting the contributions to 0.2 cents per kilowatt-hour of electricity supplied to the grid. This section allows operators of EEG-supported wind parks to make voluntary payments, though it is not obligatory. In cases where payments are made, operators can seek reimbursement from the grid operator. Given that Brandenburg had already established its own regulations regarding payments to municipalities under the Wind Turbine Levy Law (BbgWindAbgG), the amendment to the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) created an additional, non-mandatory opportunity for financial participation.

4.5 PHASE 3: EASTER PACKAGE: ATTEMPTS TO ACCELERATE WIND ENERGY THROUGH CHANGES IN FEDERAL LAW (2022 – 2023)

Following a phase of relative stagnation in the development of wind energy between 2020 and 2021, the topic gained new momentum as part of the federal election in September 2021. A coalition between the following parties was forged: Alliance 90/ The Greens (Bündnis 90/ Die Grünen), Social Democratic Party (Sozialdemokratische Partei) and Free Democrats (Freie Demokraten). The ambition of this coalition government has been to advance the expansion of renewable energy, culminating in the adoption of the so-called Easter Package in the summer of 2022. It was deemed a pivotal moment, representing the most substantial legislative overhaul in energy policy in decades (BMWK, 2022a). To achieve the aim of accelerating renewable energy, developments included, among other things, changes to the Renewable Energy Act (EEG), the Energy Industry Act (Energiewirtschaftsgesetz (EnWG)), the Federal Nature Conservation Act (BNatSchG), the Federal Emission Control Act (BImSchG) and the Federal Building Code (BauGB). Additionally, the Onshore Wind Energy Act (WaLG) was newly created.

With these legislative changes, binding quantitative area targets for the designation of wind energy areas were introduced to the federal states for the first time. Moreover, the principle that the use of renewable energy is of overriding public interest and serves public safety was legally anchored as part of the Renewable Energy Act (EEG). This federal legislation paved the way for far-reaching changes in wind energy developments in Brandenburg.

4.5.1 CONTEXT: DESCRIPTION OF THE SITUATION IN GERMANY THAT LED TO THE INTRODUCTION OF THE EASTER PACKAGE

Following the federal election in Germany in September 2021, a new coalition government was formed. Notably, this marked the Alliance 90/ The Greens (Bündnis 90/ Die Grünen) return to the federal government since 2005. As part of this process, they secured the newly named economic ministry: Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz, BMWK). The expansion of renewable energy played a pivotal role in the Alliance 90/ The Greens party's election campaign.

Soon after the election, the three parties signed the coalition agreement that stated a shared commitment to significantly accelerate the expansion of renewable energy and eliminate any obstacles and barriers (SPD et al., 2021). To achieve this, the renewable energy target for 2030 was aligned with a higher gross electricity demand (80 per cent of the annual 680-750 TWh). Moreover, there was a plan to dynamically adjust the annual auction volumes. Emphasis was also placed on strengthening the decentralised expansion of renewable energy and accelerating planning and approval procedures. The coalition agreement set a target of designating 2 percent of Germany's land area for onshore wind energy (SPD et al., 2021). In the first half of 2022, there should be collaborative efforts between the federal government, federal state governments, and municipalities to initiate all necessary measures for designating the provision of required land areas for wind energy (SPD et al., 2021).

In February 2022, shortly after the new government began its work, Russia launched an invasion and has occupied parts of Ukraine. Prior to the war, significant proportions of natural gas, hard coal, and oil, 55 per cent, 50 per cent, and 35 per cent respectively, were imported from Russia, but these supply streams were disrupted due to the escalation of the conflict (Büüsker, 2022). As a result, the expansion of renewable energy was labelled a 'matter of utmost importance for national energy security' by the Federal Minister for Economic Affairs and the Climate (BMWK) Robert Habeck (Tagesschau online, 2022). While the goal of accelerating the expansion of renewable energy had already been established in the coalition agreement, it was even further stressed after the Russian invasion of Ukraine as energy security issues started to be highly debated (Interviewee 1, Deutschlandfunk 2022). As argued by Robert Habeck during a political talk show,

"I expect a federal consensus that we now get serious and stop discussing procedures to expand power grids, power plants, and renewable energy" (Maischberger, 2022).

According to a study conducted by the Agency for Renewable Energy (Agentur für Erneuerbare Energien (AAG)), the increase in energy prices resulting from the Russian invasion of Ukraine, compounded by high inflation rates in Germany, has had an impact on the overall acceptance of renewable energy in Germany, including wind energy. A survey conducted in November 2022 by AAG revealed that more than 70 percent of the German population supported the expansion of wind energy, not showing significant differences between regions. 50 per cent of the respondents already supported wind energy before the crisis. 20 percent were previously not fans of wind energy but now believed that its expansion would be necessary. 8 per cent were strictly against its expansion but have since changed their minds to now believe that at least to some extent it is necessary (AEE, 2022). Numbers for the federal regions such as Brandenburg have not been separately published. Whilst in early 2022 the debates around the expansion of renewable energy, especially wind

energy, were influenced by energy security debates derived from the war, the legislation enacted in 2022 as part of the Easter Package was very much rooted in what had already been lined out in the coalition agreement before the invasion.

4.5.2 CRITICAL INSTANCE OF CHANGE: THE EASTER PACKAGE AS AN ACCELERATOR FOR THE EXPANSION OF RENEWABLE ENERGY

In April 2022, Robert Habeck (BMWK) introduced a comprehensive set of immediate energy measures known as the Easter Package (BMWK, 2022b). The package aimed to implement the energy policy agreements of the coalition government,

"On the one hand, the climate crisis is escalating. On the other hand, the Russian invasion highlights the importance of phasing out fossil fuels and consistently promoting the expansion of renewables. We are doing this boldly and consistently" (BMWK, 2022b).

One central element of the Easter Package has been the amendment of the Renewable Energy Act (EEG), which entails a much faster expansion of renewable energy. The main obstacles to onshore wind energy could not be resolved in the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) itself (for instance, insufficient land designation) and therefore a separate legislative package was introduced the Onshore Wind Energy Act (WaLG) and changes were made to the Federal Building Code (BauGB) to ensure the provision of the areas required for the expansion of onshore wind energy (BMWK, 2022b). The goal has been to achieve an 80 per cent share of renewable energy in the electricity supply by 2030. To achieve this goal and accelerate the expansion of wind energy, some of the following measures were introduced (BMWK, 2022c):

Some key changes to the EEG relevant for wind energy

- **Increase auction volumes:** The auction volumes for onshore wind energy were significantly raised across Germany. In 2023, a total of 12,840 MW will be auctioned, and from 2024 to 2028, 10,000 MW of installed capacity will be auctioned each year. Additionally, any auction volumes that remain unsuccessful in a given year starting from 2023 will be re-auctioned in the following year. This was a significant increase compared to the previous auction volumes set by the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) in 2021.
- **Priority of public interest:** The principle that the use of renewable energy is of overriding public interest and serves public safety was anchored in §2 of the Renewable Energy Act (EEG). This principle plays a crucial role in the balancing of interests during approval procedures. The federal government aimed for this principle to lead to more readily approved wind energy installations, even in cases where private or other public interests may be affected.
- **Financial participation of municipalities:** The requirements for the financial participation of municipalities underwent further refinement at the federal government level. The newly amended Renewable Energy Act (EEG) determined that plant operators are not only permitted to (as had been the case before) but are now encouraged to financially engage with communities affected by the construction of their facilities (§ 6 EEG 2023). Communities are considered affected if their municipal area is at least partially within a radius of 2,500 meters around the centre of the wind

turbine. If multiple communities are affected, should the operators opt for payments, they must offer payment to all affected communities or districts. The amount offered per community must be divided based on each community's share of the area within the radius of the turbine. The law also extended this option to existing installations and facilities outside the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) subsidy scheme. Nevertheless, financial participation remained voluntary, with the law setting a maximum payment limit of 0.2 cents per kWh.

- **Citizen energy projects and companies:** The amendment of the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) also introduced changes for citizen energy projects. The term 'citizen energy companies' (Bürgerenergiegesellschaften) was redefined and an exemption from the obligation to tender for citizen energy companies was included. Energy cooperatives have been explicitly included in the definition of citizen energy companies (Hasse, 2022). In addition to the EEG, the federal government adopted a funding programme for citizen energy companies. Up to 70 per cent of the costs for the planning and approval of wind energy projects can be subsidised, up to a maximum of 200,000 euros. The subsidy must be repaid if an EEG subsidy has been registered or if an award has been made in an EEG tendering procedure (Bündnis Bürgerenergie e.V., 2022).

Introduction of the Onshore Wind Energy Act and changes to the Federal Building Code

- **Binding wind area targets:** The Onshore Wind Energy Act (WaLG) introduced binding quantitative area targets for the designation of wind energy areas. These targets, known as area contribution values (Flächenbeitragswerte), aim to realise a 2 per cent target for onshore wind energy, which had been agreed upon in the coalition agreement and afterwards in the Wind Energy Area Requirement Act (Windenergieflächenbedarfsgesetz, (WindBG)). According to the study by Bons et al. (2023), 0.79 per cent of Germany's land area in 2021 was not enough to install the wind energy capacity planned by the German government. If 2 per cent of Germany's surface area were made available for wind turbines, the expansion targets could be achieved. Accordingly, it was decided that 1.4 per cent of the federal area is to be designated for wind energy by the end of 2027 and 2 per cent by the end of 2032 (BMWSB, 2023). The responsibility for allocating adequate sites and ensuring streamlined planning and permitting processes lies with the federal states. In cases where a federal state is unable or unwilling to reserve the required 2 per cent of land for onshore wind, they are permitted to exchange up to 50 per cent of their designated sites with federal states that have surpassed their targets. These additional sites must be acquired through federal state contracts using statistical transfers. It remains uncertain whether this mechanism will lead to a more equitable distribution of onshore wind projects or if it will further concentrate installations in the northern regions of the country (Deutscher Bundestag, Online-Dienste, 2022).
- **Changes to the planning process:** In addition to the Wind Energy Area Requirement Act (WindBG), changes were made to the Federal Building Code (BauGB) that integrated the area targets into planning law and simplified planning procedures for the designation of wind energy areas (Wegner, 2022). As a result, planning through the designation of wind energy areas should only have an exclusionary effect (Ausschlusswirkung) if the area targets are met. Otherwise, wind turbines should be permitted on a privileged basis in the entire planning area. The aim is to ensure that

the required amount of land is made available for the expansion of wind energy. Before the changes to the Federal Building Code (BauGB), exclusionary effect (Ausschlusswirkung) meant that installations privileged under the Federal Building Code (BauGB) in outdoor areas may only be erected within the wind priority areas – such exclusionary effect (Ausschlusswirkung) were no longer applicable to wind turbines in principle. Minimum distance regulations under federal state law on the basis of the so-called federal state opening clause of the Federal Building Code (BauGB) should continue to be possible. However, they should be linked to the fulfilment of obligations under the Wind Energy Area Requirement Act (WindBG), in particular, the area targets must be achieved.

- **Nature conservation law amendment in favour of faster wind power expansion:** The Federal Nature Conservation Act (BNatSchG) legally ensures that protected landscape areas can also be included in the search for areas for wind energy expansion. At the same time, protection zones for endangered species must be defined and high ecological standards need to be guaranteed. To simplify and speed up permitting procedures for wind turbines, uniform national standards are set up for species conservation assessments (BMUV, 2022).

Figure 8: Overview of the legislative measures implemented as part of the federal government's Easter package for the accelerated expansion of wind energy, own compilation

4.5.3 THE EASTER PACKAGE: DEVELOPMENTS IN BRANDENBURG

In Brandenburg, the Onshore Wind Energy Act (WaLG) mandates the designation of a minimum of 1.8 per cent of the land area in the federal state by the end of 2027 and at least 2.2 per cent by the end of 2032 (MIL Brandenburg, 2023). As a consequence of the introduction of the Wind Energy Area Requirement Act (WindBG) and changes to the Federal Building Code (BauGB), in Brandenburg, the federal state lifted the wind energy moratorium to safeguard the regional plans currently being drawn up in November 2022 in view of the abolition of the exclusionary effect (Ausschlusswirkung). They also made it clear that there would be no state planning prohibitions to safeguard the new plans. However, the Brandenburg Wind Turbine Distance Act (BbgWindAbgG) that regulates the distance from turbines from residential areas to be 1,000 meters stayed in place for the time being. The distancing rules would only be overturned if the area contribution values are not achieved by the given deadlines. Still, criticism of this act was expressed by the German Wind Energy Association (BWE), stating that the introduction of a 1,000-meter fixed distance severely limits the potential for wind energy and does not promote acceptance (BWE, 2022).

In October 2022, the federal state of Brandenburg also changed its regional planning from its former exclusion planning (Ausschlussplanung), which involved identifying wind suitability areas (Windeignungsgebiete), to move to offer planning (Angebotsplanung) with so-called priority areas (Vorranggebiete) (MIL Brandenburg, 2023). Although the federal Onshore Wind Energy Act (WaLG) that legislated such planning changes towards offer planning would have not started until February 2023, the Brandenburg state parliament had already passed a resolution (Entschließungsantrag) that mandated the federal state government to take the necessary legislative steps in order to change the regional planning from exclusion planning to offer planning in 2022 (SPD-Fraktion et al., 2021).

“The federal government essentially surpassed the debates in Brandenburg in several aspects by addressing what had already been driven forward on the federal state level but not successfully yet: the shift from wind suitability areas to wind priority areas” (Interviewee 1).

Under the previous regional planning system in Brandenburg, it was the mandate of the five regional planning communities to designate wind suitability areas. Wind energy installations could only be built within these suitability areas, the remaining land was excluded for wind energy developments. With the binding land area targets that were decided at the federal level, it became increasingly evident that such targets could not be met through the current exclusion planning approach (Interviewee 1). Even within designated suitability areas, there was no assurance that wind turbine permits would be granted on such designated lands. For instance, protected animal species are often newly discovered within wind suitability areas, leading to restrictions on permits. Consequently, how much land was designated within the regional plans and how much land was used for wind energy in practice was not always equivalent in the past (Interviewee 1).

A change to offer planning meant that the mandate of regional planning is to designate so-called wind priority areas (Vorranggebiete) namely areas where wind energy takes precedence over other private and public interests. One of the interviewees argued,

“I say that regional planning will of course become easier and inevitably faster, because I have to prioritise the priority areas and justify them well... So, in this respect it is a completely different situation for regional planning, and in my view an easier one” (Interviewee 3).

Outside these priority areas, wind energy can also be installed, but only if municipalities themselves draft such land-use plans or if the federal state is unable to designate the necessary target areas. As explained by one of the interviewees,

"If the states manage to reach the land area targets with the existing areas, then there will continue to be an exclusion effect, meaning outside the priority areas, wind energy installations can only be built if the municipalities establish corresponding land-use plans. If the federal state fails to reach the defined land area targets with the designated areas, then essentially, we revert to what was originally in place, namely the privilege in outdoor areas. That means, anywhere is possible" (Interviewee 1).

"Exclusion planning" with suitability areas

"Offer planning" with priority areas

Figure 9: Reorganisation of regional planning processes in Brandenburg (from 'exclusion planning with suitability areas to 'offer planning' with priority areas, own compilation)

The transition of regional planning to offer planning and the new targets pose a challenge for the regional planning communities in Brandenburg, considering that they must create new regional plans featuring wind priority areas. The starting point for this endeavour proves to be difficult, considering past court rulings deeming the regional plans invalid in the past, none of the five planning communities have so far finalised their plan. The change in planning for wind energy thus occurs during a time where plans were drawn up and now must be re-drawn based on a different approach. While it's theoretically feasible to designate the previously planned wind suitability areas as wind priority areas, it is anticipated that this process is legally intricate and can take several years to complete (Interviewee 1, 3).

Given the priority status of wind energy, one of the parties in Brandenburg – the Brandenburg United Citizen’s Movements/ Free Voters (Brandenburger Vereinigte Bürgerbewegungen/ Freie Wähler) raised concerns about the potential for uncontrolled wind energy expansion i.e. wild growth (Wildwuchs) in Brandenburg (Hewel, 2022). Similarly, one of the interviewees argued,

“And the fact that planning sovereignty was taken away from us, as it is now, I think is a serious mistake... And as long as the federal state targets for wind energy developments are not met, it's just like the Wild West” (Interviewee 5).

While such arguments exist, other interviewees have said that although there are no regional planning restrictions on the construction of wind turbines as long as valid plans are not in effect, it is expected that wind turbine operators will still rely on older regional plans to minimise costs and potential conflicts (Interviewee 1, 3, and 6). Moreover, wind turbines may only continue to be planned and authorised if they comply with federal and federal state law. Until new regional plans come into force, a building law privilege anchored in the Federal Building Code (BauGB) will once again apply outside of built-up areas. Wind turbines still require planning permission in accordance with emission control legislation and must comply with regulations such as the Brandenburg Wind Turbine Distance Act, species protection, protected areas, monument protection, air traffic control and regional planning (Land Brandenburg, 2023, Interviewee 1). Interviewee 1 explained,

“The reasons for rejection are often not that they are somehow outside the wind suitability area, but that there are other reasons. So, it is still the case that nature conservation areas still are taboo. Bird sanctuaries. The 1,000-meter distance rule still applies and so on. So, it's not the case that it's allowed to install wind turbines everywhere... So, most of the refusals are probably due to other reasons that have not changed” (Interviewee 1).

In conclusion, the legislative changes at the federal level sparked significant dynamics and changes in Brandenburg. Predicting the course of these legislative dynamics at present is challenging. Consequently, most individuals interviewed for this case study were cautious in offering forecasts about the future development of wind energy in the upcoming years.

Developments of a climate action plan in Brandenburg: Potentially influencing the developments of wind energy developments

The federal state government of Brandenburg, led by the Ministry of Agriculture, Environment, and Climate Protection (Ministerium für Landwirtschaft, Umwelt und Klimaschutz, MLUK), is currently in the process of developing the Brandenburg Climate Plan. This plan aims to be a comprehensive strategy for climate protection, spanning various sectors, and accompanied by an action program with the goal of achieving climate neutrality no later than 2045. The decision to develop the Climate Plan was made by the state government in 2019. The Climate Plan is supposed to serve as a guiding framework for sector-specific climate strategies implemented by different ministries, such as energy, buildings, mobility, and agriculture. To ensure effective development, an Interministerial Working Group (Interministerielle Arbeitsgruppe, IMAG) has been established facilitating close coordination among the federal state government throughout the entire process. A consortium of experts, led by the Institute for Ecological Economy Research (IÖW), has prepared a scientific report to provide the foundation for the Climate Plan, offering more than 80 sets of measures covering all eight areas of action outlined in the Climate Plan and

highlighting crucial tasks for state policy in the journey towards climate neutrality (MLUK Brandenburg, 2023).

Regarding the development of wind energy, the scientific report put forward a set of far-reaching recommendations including (Hirschl et al., 2023):

- the promotion of multiple technologies in one area (e.g. photovoltaic and wind energy),
- the utilisation of wind energy in commercial forests,
- embedding the principle of an overriding public interest in federal state laws to ensure its adequate consideration during permitting processes,
- prioritising participation to better and earlier incorporate insights by stakeholders and therefore shorten the overall permit phase,
- providing advisory assistance and education to inform the public about their options, particularly regarding the formation of community energy projects as well as significantly expanding existing advisory capacities for different stakeholders,
- increasing financial participation of citizens to enhance acceptance and activate private capital for the energy transition.

At this point in time, it remains to be seen to what extent the recommendations of the scientific report will be considered in the development of the Climate Plan. Based on the far-reaching measures, the report could serve as a potential critical instance of change.

Brandenburg: Instances of Participation

In Germany, wind energy participation can be divided into formal and informal ways of participating. While forms of formal participation are legally mandated and include planning and approval procedures, informal measures such as public consultation and community advisory panels can be initiated by, for instance, municipalities and project developers to add to the formal processes. In addition to the formal and informal participation procedures, in Germany, various forms of financial participation have been discussed and introduced (Salecki, et al., 2020). These can be categorised into active financial participation, where citizens actively contribute to the production or financing of projects (i.e. through cooperative models), and passive financial participation, where citizens and municipalities benefit locally from wind energy projects through revenue-sharing models or land lease agreements. The following examples from Brandenburg showcase how citizen participation can influence wind energy developments:

Schlalach, Brandenburg: Informal participation

Schlalach in Brandenburg serves as a widely acknowledged positive example of informal participation in wind energy project planning. In Schlalach, property owners and residents within a designated wind development area formed a joint working group to facilitate the implementation of a planned wind park that would benefit the entire community and contribute to regional value creation. In 2002, the regional planning community of Havelland-

Fläming designated a wind suitability area that was characterised by fragmented ownership of the land. This situation resulted in 135 landowners receiving numerous inquiries from different wind energy project developers. To ensure a collaborative and inclusive approach, the joint working group established guidelines to develop wind energy projects in the area. They decided on a land lease model that ensures a fair distribution of the lease income to all landowners within the wind energy suitability areas irrespective of the specific location of the wind turbines (AEE, 2010; Ermisch et al., 2018). To consider the interests of residents, who do not directly benefit from the lease, a community foundation was established. The foundation receives 0.75 per cent of the Feed-In-Tariff (FIT) from the operator, which is then utilised to finance charitable projects within the village (AEE, 2010). Further conditions for project implementation included considerations for regional construction companies and favourable conditions for the agricultural practices around the wind park. The working group formulated these requirements in a call for tenders, allowing interested wind energy developers to apply (Ermisch et al., 2018).

Uebigau-Wahrenbrück, Brandenburg: Informal participation

The municipality of Uebigau-Wahrenbrück represents a case where wind energy projects were successfully implemented, despite local protests in the planning phase. The wind energy park in Uebigau-Wahrenbrück consists of 21 wind turbines, which were erected in three stages (between 2005 and 2007; in 2014, and between 2016 and 2017) (Colell et al., 2022). Despite initial support for wind energy from the municipality and regional planning community, protests against wind energy emerged in the region. Opposition groups, representing various interests and political parties, expressed concerns about the unequal distribution of wind turbines, potential negative impacts on the landscape, effects on tourism, and noise disturbances (Colell et al., 2022; Reitz et al., 2022). Citizen participation in the planning procedures in Uebigau-Wahrenbrück was organised through a citizen office and took on various forms. Apart from legally required public participation procedures, these include information and training events, renewable energy fairs, and idea exchange formats. Although residents expressed interest in a citizen participation model, attempts to implement one failed until 2018, when the project developer introduced a citizen savings model called citizen wind savings (Bürgerwindsparen) (Colell et al., 2022; Reitz et al., 2022). This financial participation model offers individuals the opportunity to invest in wind parks as a savings model. The model incorporates a limited-term feature and fixed interest rates, which effectively reduce project risks and aid the process of continuous citizen participation. Moreover, the investment range (between 500 to 15000 euros) is aimed at enhancing accessibility by setting a lower threshold, making the participation model more inclusive and accessible to a wider population (Wolf et al., 2021).

Formal participation in Brandenburg

Formal public participation is mandatory under federal and state spatial planning acts, such as the Federal Building Code (BauGB) and Federal Emission Control Act (BImSchG) in Germany. It is carried out by the approval authorities. Formal public participation occurs in the land use planning process (Flächennutzungsplanung) and often in the regional planning process (Regionalplanverfahren). In Brandenburg, wind energy development and the designation of wind energy suitability areas are managed by the regional planning communities, which often results in limited formal participation opportunities and decision-making authority for municipalities in planning procedures (Dr. A. Colell et al., 2022, Interview 2). Financial participation possibilities for municipalities have improved through an amendment to the Renewable Energy Act (§ 6 EEG 2021), allowing project developers to voluntarily pay affected communities within a radius of 2,500 meters an amount of up to 0.2 ct/kWh for actually fed-

in amounts of electricity (Dr. A. Colell et al., 2022, Interview 2). In 2019, the Brandenburg state government implemented the Wind Turbine Levy Law (BbgWindAbgG), which legally mandates the financial participation of municipalities. The law establishes a lump sum levy for newly erected wind turbines, to be paid to municipalities in the surrounding area. The special levy amounts to 10,000 euro per WT per year. By involving municipalities in the revenues generated by wind turbines, the law aims at increasing regional value creation and acceptance for newly constructed wind turbines.

Anti-wind developments surrounding Beelitz in Potsdam

In the district of Potsdam-Mittelmark in Brandenburg, there were several years of conflicts regarding the designation of wind energy areas. In 2010, the sub-area land use plan, which was the regional plan for wind energy by the planning community Havelland-Fläming, was repealed. In response, the city of Beelitz commissioned its own planning for the designation of wind energy suitable areas. There were strong objections to the proposed plans, including from local citizen initiatives. In March 2011, the citizen initiative 'Naturally against noise Fichtenwalde' ('Natürlich gegen Lärm Fichtenwalde') was founded, and the designation of wind energy suitable areas quickly became the dominant topic. The main reasons for opposing wind energy included noise pollution, the risk of forest fires, and dissatisfaction with planning and participation procedures. In a public discussion event in 2011, the initiative demanded, "As affected municipalities and localities of Fichtenwalde, Beelitz-Heilstätten, Borkwalde, and Borkheide, we demand comprehensive and early citizen participation" (Eichenauer et al., 2018, p. 4). In early 2012, 23 citizen initiatives opposed to wind energy in Fichtenwalde, led by 'Naturally against noise Fichtenwalde' gathered and drafted a petition to the state government of Brandenburg to halt further expansion of wind energy in the region. In July 2014, several initiatives, including those from Fichtenwalde, Borkheide/Borkwalde, Bliesdorf, and Kloster Lehnin, joined forces to establish the association 'Waldkleeblatt - Natürlich Zauche e.V.' In August 2015, Waldkleeblatt was recognised as an environmental organisation, granting it the right to file class-action lawsuits. As a result, Waldkleeblatt was able to take legal action against environmentally relevant permitting decisions, including those related to wind energy (Eichenauer et al., 2018). The anti-wind energy developments near Beelitz in Potsdam-Mittelmark exemplify the growing mobilisation against wind energy in specific sub-regions. These initiatives often focus not only on wind energy itself but also express a broader critique of energy policy goals (Reusswig, Braun, Eichenauer, et al., 2016).

To sum up: the examples of participatory practices in Brandenburg demonstrate the diversity of possible formal and informal forms of participation. However, they also highlight the challenges posed by forms of resistance and conflicts revolving around a lack of participation opportunities for municipalities and citizens. In general, it is essential to involve local populations early and continuously in decision-making processes in order to achieve procedural justice. The joint working group in Schlalach serves as a positive example in this regard. However, many conflicts also revolve around distributive justice, particularly regarding the distribution of costs and benefits, including the distribution of wind park locations, ownership issues, income distribution, and compensatory measures. The examples demonstrate that distributive justice can be achieved through policies enhancing formal participation, increased local value creation, and forms of financial participation, such as citizen wind savings schemes, as well as financial compensation. It remains important to note that the expansion of wind energy often depends on context-specific variables. Understanding local contexts is crucial for identifying appropriate forms of participatory practices and reconciling the interests of various stakeholder groups.

5 ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

What types of procedures and processes have emerged and developed to be able to make decisions on how much, where, and how to build wind energy projects in Brandenburg? What have been key actors and their activities and roles in the development of wind energy in Brandenburg?

How much, where, and how to build wind energy in Brandenburg is determined by several actors, procedures, and processes.

The **federal government** (including the Federal Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action (BMWK)) sets targets for the whole of Germany and is responsible for developing a framework for wind energy as part of laws and regulations (such as the Federal Building Code (BauGB) or the Renewable Energy Act (EEG)), for example, subsidising the development of wind energy and regulating the speed of the expansion. More recently, the federal government has set wind energy area percentage targets for wind energy for the federal states and has set in motion several regulatory changes that aim to speed up the planning and permission process for wind energy.

Federal states, like Brandenburg, have the autonomy to develop their own energy strategies. Within these, they can outline a vision for the energy composition within the federal state, determining e.g. the role and pace of initiatives such as the coal phase-out, in conjunction with strategies and targets for the deployment of wind energy. However, they are also obliged to adhere to the laws and regulations outlined by the federal government. With the Onshore Wind Energy Act (WaLG), which came into effect on February 1, 2023, the federal states were mandated by the federal government to allocate a predefined share of their land area for wind energy (2 percent). To facilitate the development of wind energy, the regional planning authority serves as a key institution. In this context, federal states can navigate how they intend to comply with legal requirements through the use of spatial planning, regional plans, or land-use plans.

Brandenburg is using an approach where they delegate **regional planning authority** related to wind energy to a Joint Spatial Planning Department Berlin-Brandenburg as well as five **regional planning communities**, which determine the locations and methods for wind energy installations. Until recently, Brandenburg's approach to wind energy planning involved wind designating areas suitable for wind development, a task carried out by the regional planning communities through the creation of regional wind plans. These plans, along with their corresponding wind suitability areas, were developed and decided upon in regional assemblies, the primary bodies of regional planning composed of representatives from municipalities. The regional assemblies are supported by regional planning offices. The role of the Joint Spatial Planning Department Berlin-Brandenburg has been to review regional wind plans regarding specific criteria derived from national laws, state guidance, and court rules. These regulations, guidelines, and rules, to some extent, influence the autonomy of the regional planning communities. Brandenburg's regional planning offices have faced challenges such as limited staffing capacities (as wind energy is just one aspect of their responsibilities), lengthy processes in developing the plans (involving up to 1,000 position statements to process), and regional plans that were not legally binding (Planning officer, event notes, 2022). With the enactment of the new federal legislation in the summer of 2022, Brandenburg transitioned its regional planning from an exclusion-based approach

(Ausschlussplanung) to an offer-based approach (Angebotsplanung). This shift means that regional planning communities are no longer required to designate wind suitability areas. Instead, they must identify wind priority areas where wind energy is given priority over other interests. It is yet to be seen how this fundamental shift in regional planning will influence wind energy developments in Brandenburg. At the moment, it has caused uncertainties.

The approval process of wind energy has been overseen by the **Brandenburg Environment Agency** (Landesamt für Umweltschutz) in accordance with the Federal Emission Control Act (Bundes-Immissionsschutzgesetz, BImSchG), whose primary objective is to safeguard humans, animals, plants, soil, water, atmosphere, as well as cultural and other material assets from adverse environmental impacts. The emission control permitting process has a cumulative effect, this means that the other permits and approvals required for the operation of wind energy parks are reviewed and decided upon as part of the emission control process. This might include further regulations of nature and species protection law, building regulations, as well as planning law. Furthermore, other specialist legal matters such as aviation law and landscape and heritage conservation may also be relevant. The Brandenburg Environment Agency is also responsible for considering the results of a mandatory, usually extensive and complex environmental impact assessment (Umweltverträglichkeitsprüfung). To speed up the planning process and the expansion of wind energy, measures were implemented by the federal government in January 2023 as part of an EU emergency regulation, which eliminates environmental impact assessments for a range of permitting procedures. For example, for projects located in areas that have already undergone a Strategic Environmental Assessment (Strategische Umweltprüfung) during the designation of wind priority areas (or suitability areas) by the regional planning authorities and are not situated in a Natura 2000 area, nature reserve, or national park, the obligation for an environmental impact assessment is waived for these projects until June 30, 2024. In such cases, only a modified species conservation assessment is required. If this is not feasible, operators must make a financial contribution to a species conservation program.

An important component for determining wind areas as part of the regional planning procedures is the Federal Nature Conservation Act (BNatSchG), which has derived from the **European Union**. EU policies and laws surrounding wind energy have had to be implemented by the federal and federal state governments. In addition to nature conservation, this has also included policies such as the EU Emergency Regulation (2022) to speed up procedures for the expansion of renewable energy and the electricity grid and the EU Renewable Energy Directive (2018) that sets out the requirement of 32 percent of the energy consumed within the EU to be renewable by 2030.

The location, quantity, and construction of wind energy projects are also influenced by **wind energy developers**, which can include regional and international companies with diverse business models. These developers can take the form of investors, constructors, operators, or a mix of actors and make decisions based on factors like wind energy potential, site accessibility, negotiation of contracts with landowners, feasibility assessments, technical and financial analyses, and the ease of planning procedures, including compliance with distancing rules. They conduct evaluations on various aspects such as wind potentials, species protection, grid connections, planning laws, and emissions. Wind energy developers used to be required to seek approval for specific wind turbines within designated wind suitability areas. With the new offer-based approach new regional plans will have to be developed that designate priority areas. Wind energy developers will still be bound by those

designated areas with the difference that municipalities outside of designated priority areas can proactively pursue wind energy if they accordingly draft their own land use plans. Moreover, if the federal state is not able to comply with the federal wind energy area targets, the exclusionary effect of the designated priority areas expires, and developers can - at least in theory – seek approval anywhere.

Municipalities have also played a key role in wind energy developments. In the past, many municipalities have been contacted by wind energy project developers about potential projects but due to a lack of personnel and know-how around energy issues, many municipalities have not had the capacity to respond. For many years, municipalities were not financially involved in wind energy in Brandenburg. This changed when the act on the payment of a special levy to municipalities near wind energy parks was introduced in 2019 i.e. the Wind Turbine Levy Law (BbgWindAbgG). With the amendment of the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) in 2021 and 2023, another option for municipalities to financially participate was established while limiting the contribution to 0.2 cents per kilowatt-hour of electricity supplied to the grid. The newly established paragraph within the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) allows and encourages operators of wind parks to make voluntary payments, though it is not obligatory.

Moreover, Brandenburg has set up an energy agency. The **Brandenburg Energy Agency** is the central point of contact for companies and municipalities on the efficient use of energy, increasing the share of renewable energy and on corresponding funding programs. The energy agency also participates in the implementation of the Energy Strategy 2040 and the monitoring of its implementation. One of the measures of the 6-Point Plan in 2018 was the introduction of an advisory service as part of the Brandenburg Energy Agency, advising and supporting municipalities and companies during informal and formal participation processes. In addition, the regional planning communities employ **regional energy managers**, who implement with other regional actors the regional energy concepts. One of their tasks is to realise regional projects in the areas of energy efficiency, energy saving, renewable energy and acceptance. As highlighted by one of the interviewees,

“In the five regional planning communities alone, each has its dedicated regional energy management, consisting of one person in each case. They are not financed on a permanent basis but only on a project-by-project basis. Incidentally, this also leads to a very high fluctuation... they can do a lot of the things we've mentioned and discussed, sometimes only partially, it's just one person for one region at a time. But they're super helpful” (Interviewee 1).

Although interviewees did not mention them specifically (this might be a shortcoming with regards to the sampling of the interviewees), the document and media analysis showed that **environmental and nature conservation NGOs** (including birds and bats, trees, etc.) increasingly played a role when discussions arose about creating wind energy turbines in forests in Brandenburg. In 2016, Brandenburg's nature conservation associations started to oppose the expansion of wind turbines in forests. They argued that the construction of access roads and wind turbines alone would cause great damage to the ecological function of the forests. In addition, bats and birds hunting in the higher airspace would face risks of collision with the rotor blades of wind turbines (BUND und NABU Brandenburg, 2016).

Grid operating companies (grids and transmission lines) could also be mentioned at this point. From 2000 onwards instead of merely requiring grid operating companies to

incorporate green electricity into their grids, the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) now mandated them to prioritise it over conventionally generated electricity. Nevertheless, grid expansion issues occurred early on, meaning that the production of electricity through wind turbines has had to be routinely cut to avoid overloading the grid. This has also been the case in Brandenburg. According to the Federal Network Agency, 4 percent of renewable energy that was produced could not be used in 2022.

The role of **residents near wind turbines, landowners and the public** within these processes are discussed in more depth in the next section.

What roles (or not) have residents played within these procedures and processes?

Since 2018, acceptance issues linked to wind energy have been high on the political agenda in Brandenburg. Residents can be defined differently and linked to different roles. For instance, they can be landowners, mayors or have other roles in the municipality or they can be part of an anti-wind energy group near the proposed wind park. Distancing rules and regional borders can sometimes determine whether residents are impacted by wind turbines (or not). Residents' involvement in wind energy can therefore be diverse. They can have a stake in it by owning the land where the wind turbine is built and potentially setting up lucrative contracts with developers. Moreover, residents can mobilise against wind energy projects, gathering lots of information, for instance, on the potential effects on the local wildlife.

Wind energy developers need to set up contracts with landowners (for instance, farmers) to be able to build their wind turbines and parks. Newspapers have reported about landowners in Brandenburg getting regular calls and visits from wind energy developers, demonstrating that interest in access to land has been high in the region. Landowners have been offered one-off payments and yearly payments over a certain period of time (Haan & Simmler, 2018). In Schlalach, Brandenburg, a group of landowners got together to think about ways to engage with wind energy developers as a group to be able to be part of decision-making processes surrounding wind energy in the area. Such collective efforts are rare. To narrow down the question, it might be possible to ask how residents have been able to participate in wind energy developments in Brandenburg. Legally based participation opportunities for citizens exist both through representative means and directly:

- **Participation via representation:** Wind suitability areas used to be designated by the five regional planning communities consisting of the regional planning offices and the regional assemblies. The same goes for the regional plans that now need to designate wind priority areas. The regional assemblies are essential decision-making bodies of the regional planning communities. They determine the fundamental aspects of planning work and adopt the regional plans. The regional assemblies each consist of representatives from municipalities (district administrators and mayors) as well as a specific proportion of freely elected representatives from the counties (Landkreise).
- **Direct participation via formal public participation procedures:** Formal public participation in Germany is obligatory under the federal and state spatial planning acts such as the Federal Building Code (BauGB) and Federal Emission Control Act (BImSchG) and is carried out by the approval authorities. Formal public participation takes place in the land use plan processes (Flächennutzungsplanung) and often in the

regional plan processes (Regionalplanverfahren). Formal public participation is legally stipulated and usually structured in two stages (but not necessarily). For instance, the preliminary draft of a land use plan is to be presented as part of early public participation. The purpose of this phase is to improve the draft plan, to identify the suggestions from citizens and inform the public. Subsequently, the preliminary draft is processed and publicly displayed in the second phase of public participation. During this process citizens can submit position statements. All comments received on time will be reviewed and evaluated by the planning officers, and the draft will be adapted. The completed draft of the land use plan is then submitted to the higher administrative authority for approval. Moreover, formal participation also is part of the approval process for wind parks. Potential operators must apply for approval before building wind turbines, regardless of where they want to build. All documents that are submitted by developers with the application are made available to the public by the Brandenburg Environment Agency (except for the simplified approval procedure for up to two wind turbines that are not part of a wind park). This gives the public the opportunity to submit written objections/ position statements. In a public hearing, any objections/ statements are analysed. After that, a decision on the granting of the permit will be made by the authority.

Informal participation as part of the local planning procedure can vary between regions and municipalities. The German Wind Energy Association (Bundesverband Windenergie) has spoken about three stages linked to informal participation processes: information (such as websites and social media posts), dialog (such as question and answer sessions, hearings of experts, and round table meetings) and co-determination (visioning workshops, citizens' conferences, and citizens' expert opinions) (Ermisch et al., 2018). Although several guidelines for successful informal public participation in wind energy expansion have been published by various stakeholders (e.g. Sondershaus, 2017), there is a significant gap between theory and practice. Informal participation procedures in Brandenburg – if they are indeed initiated – vary greatly depending on the culture and practices of wind energy companies that are looking to invest but also capacities and experiences of the involved municipalities. As wind energy companies/investors (for economic reasons) as well as municipalities (for political reasons) have an interest in avoiding unnecessary conflict, a trend towards more informal participation is indeed being reported by involved actors (an aspect that was confirmed in most interviews). Whether informal participation is successful still depends significantly on how aware a municipality is of its own role in this process and how effectively it can negotiate and contribute to shaping the procedures. Below some informal participation processes are described to illustrate the range of informal participatory practices:

- In Prenzlau and Jacobsdorf in Brandenburg, the local wind park operator has offered sponsorships to local social institutions such as schools, nurseries, or other charitable projects as part of the participation process. The aim of these sponsorships have been the long-term maintenance of these social institutions.
- In Schlalach, Brandenburg, landowners in a wind suitability area created with other residents a working group to formulate conditions for the realisation of a wind energy park. The requirements developed by the group were formulated in an invitation to tender, to which interested planning offices could apply. The agreement developed with the successful applicant included a land lease model that ensured lease income for all landowners regardless of the specific location of the wind turbines.

- The residents of the municipality of Schlalach have also established a community foundation that ensures that the income from wind energy benefits the village. Every year, the foundation distributes 50,000 euros, which has already been used to build a children's playground and support local associations.
- The Brandenburg-based company ENERTRAG is offering residents living near wind turbines in some communities a so-called wind power bonus, which allows them to save up to 50% on their electricity costs.

Anti-wind energy initiatives have played an important role in Brandenburg, increasingly mobilising against wind energy, for example, collecting signatures to increase distancing rules and stop wind energy in forests. Reusswig et al. (2016) have found an increasing professionalisation of the work of such initiatives against wind energy and grid infrastructures. Social media also functions as an exchange platform for information and activities. Moreover, they have become more institutionalised, considering that individuals have become active in local politics and being elected to local and regional parliaments. Some groups are not against wind energy per se, but rather critique overall political energy goals (Reusswig, Braun, Heger, et al., 2016).

Citizen energy projects/ energy cooperatives: Germany has been known for its citizen energy cooperatives that have aided the process of democratising energy transitions (Morris & Jungjohann, 2016). This has mainly been a phenomenon of West Germany. In Brandenburg, “out of the 350 wind parks and altogether 3,890 wind turbines, less than 10 wind parks can be called citizen parks. Wind energy companies capitalise on this disparity. If local residents in East Germany demand less (economic) participation than their counterparts in energy regions in West Germany, they will also be offered less” (Müller & Morton, 2021b, p. 70; Reusswig, Braun, Eichenauer, et al., 2016).

What have been key coalitions and their activities and roles in the development of wind energy in Brandenburg?

Based on our empirical work, several coalitions can be identified in the focus period (keeping in mind that more coalitions might have played a role):

- **Coalition of municipalities to issue the Bernau and later Brandenburg Declaration:** In June 2018, the mayors of Ahrensfelde, Wandlitz, and the town of Bernau collectively endorsed the Bernau Declaration (Bernauer Erklärung) alongside 23 other municipal leaders. This declaration detailed several demands, including the prohibition of wind turbine construction in forests and the establishment of a minimum distance of 1,500 meters from residential areas. Subsequently, the declaration was distributed to all mayors throughout the federal state to transform it into a Brandenburg-wide initiative. Ultimately, the Brandenburg Declaration (Brandenburger Erklärung) emerged from the Bernau Declaration, signed by a total of 270 local leaders and presented to the President of the State Parliament in May 2018, approximately one year after the Bernau Declaration, but with identical content.
- **Increasing professionalisation and network creation of anti-wind groups:** The opposition to wind energy and grid infrastructures has experienced a growing professionalisation. This trend is due to increasingly interconnected initiatives and

the establishment of groups expanding beyond urban areas and regions. Examples include initiatives like 'Reasoning Power' (Vernunftskraft) and the citizen initiative 'Save Brandenburg' (Volksinitiative Rettet Brandenburg). Social media platforms have evolved into hubs for information exchange and coordinated activities. Furthermore, there has been an institutional shift, marked by individuals actively engaging in local politics and securing positions in local and regional parliaments.

- **Energy sector coalition in the form of the German Federal Wind Energy Association and its Berlin-Brandenburg state association (Bundesverband für Windenergie Landesverband Berlin-Brandenburg):** The association plays a significant role in Brandenburg. As a professional association representing the wind energy industry, it primarily encompasses planners, operators, and manufacturers of wind turbines. Alongside its overarching professional work (e.g. publication of wind energy journals or data on wind energy development), its role as a professional association particularly extends to political lobbying, a role it has actively pursued since its establishment in 1996. In the discussions surrounding wind energy, the association stands as the primary voice for the wind energy industry and its interests. It has consistently provided comprehensive commentary on political initiatives in the past (e.g. in relation to the 6-Point Plan).

How have regulatory institutions shaped the development of wind energy over time and space in Brandenburg?

The term 'regulatory institutions' refers to regulations, legislations, policies as well as governance mechanisms. The German energy system is highly regulated. As can be seen from the pre-period and focus period, regulatory institutions have significantly influenced the development of wind energy in Germany and Brandenburg. Regulatory and legislative changes can be instigated by EU directives (for example, 2009, 2018, 2021 and also EU packages such as Clean energy for all Europeans package (2019) and Fit for 55 package (2021)) and are developed and signed by the federal government and federal state government. A key legislation that has regulated the expansion of renewable energy and therefore wind energy has been the Renewable Energy Act (EEG). It came into force in 2000 and since then has been modified several times (2004, 2009, 2012, 2014, 2017, 2021, 2023). It was preceded by the Electricity Feed-in Act, which initiated the first Feed-In-Tariff (FIT) scheme. One major modification came into effect in 2014, moving from Feed-In-Tariff (FIT) to auctions. In addition, the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) in 2023 has been considered to be one of the biggest legislative amendments to energy in decades, including detailed regulations for onshore wind energy. The planning and permitting of wind energy are regulated through, for instance, the following regulations and legislations on the federal level: Federal Building Code (BauGB), Federal Nature Conservation Act (BNatSchG), and Federal Emission Control Act (BImSchG).

In addition to EU and federal legislations, the federal state government is able to regulate wind energy to some extent. The existing federal state government created a coalition contract for the election period of 2019-2024. Within this contract, they have committed to the wind energy expansion target of 10,500 MW in 2030 in accordance with the Energy Strategy 2030 (Fachagentur Windenergie an Land, 2023). In addition, several acts and decrees have been passed by the federal state parliament. These have included, for example,

- Animal ecological distance criteria for the erection of wind turbines in Brandenburg (TAK) (as of September 2018).
- Law on the payment of a special levy to municipalities in the vicinity of wind turbines (Wind Turbine Levy Law, BbgWindAbgG) passed in 2019.
- Brandenburg Wind Energy Plant Distance Act (BbgWEAAbG), which regulates the minimum distances between wind energy turbines and residential buildings (2022).
- Decree on species protection in approval procedures for wind turbines (AGW decree) (which came into force in June 2023).

Next to such acts, Brandenburg is in the process of developing a climate change plan and has an energy strategy in which wind energy plays a key role.

Since 2021, the federal coalition government has aimed to accelerate the expansion of wind energy in Germany, modifying the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) whilst introducing new ones such as the Onshore Wind Energy Law (WaLG). Some of the key changes have been (BMWK, 2022c):

- Some modifications of the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) have included, for example, amendments to the financial participation of the municipalities and inclusion of new expansion paths, which increases the installed capacity of onshore wind energy turbines from 69 GW in 2024 to 160 GW in 2040.
- The introduction of the Wind Energy Surface Area Requirements Act (WindBG), a legislation concerning land allocation for wind energy and ensuring that by 2032, 2 percent of Germany's land area will be designated for onshore wind energy.
- Changes to the Federal Nature Conservation Act (BNatSchG) with the aim to reconcile bird protection and wind energy expansion.
- Changes to the German Building Code (BauGB) to integrate area targets into planning law and simplify planning procedures for the designation of wind energy areas. Wind turbines should be permitted on a privileged basis in the entire planning area. Before the changes to the Federal Building Code (BauGB), exclusionary effect (Ausschlusswirkung) meant that installations privileged under the Federal Building Code (BauGB) in outdoor areas may only be erected within the wind priority areas – such exclusionary effect (Ausschlusswirkung) are no longer applicable to wind turbines in principle.

Considering that the regulative and legislative changes have been relatively recently introduced, there is limited research on the impacts on wind energy developments. Some of the interviewees felt that important steps have been taken (Interviewee 1,3). For instance, it might become easier for the regional planning communities to designate wind priority areas and compromises might be struck more easily at the regional assemblies (Interviewee 1). Nevertheless, it was also pointed out that some barriers have not been addressed such as lack of resources within permitting authorities and shortage of skilled labour. Similarly, the German Wind Energy Association (BWE) has indicated that there are several “headwinds: lengthy process times, rising raw material prices, problems with supply chains and a

worsening shortage of skilled labour [that] are slowing down the pace of expansion” (BWE, 2023). If targets can be met, is still to be seen.

How have normative and cultural-cognitive institutions shaped the development of wind energy over time and space in Brandenburg?

Normative institutions can be codes of conduct or societal expectations such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). Cultural-cognitive institutions can be customs, specific cultures or histories. In Germany, the energy transition i.e. Energiewende is understood as a political as well as a societal and cultural process. Acceptance issues linked to renewable energy such as solar parks and wind turbines have accompanied the energy transition and related energy policy debates since its beginning. Compared to other countries, the situation in Germany is characterised by a relatively dense population in regions, incentives structures for renewable energy, a strong environmental and anti-nuclear movement and Germany's federal state structure (Local Energy Consulting, 2020). The Energiewende has been very popular in Germany for years, as numerous surveys have repeatedly shown (e.g. Hildebrand und Renn, 2019; Wolf, 2020). Around 90 per cent of respondents consider the expansion of renewable energy to be important or extremely important for a successful energy transition. With the start of the Fridays for Future movement in 2018, some argue that a societal shift started to emerge, raising the profile of climate and energy issues across different societal spheres and stakeholder groups.

With regards to Brandenburg, the region has long been an energy-exporting state. Brandenburg produces significantly more energy than it needs. In addition, lignite coal has been mined in the eastern parts of the federal state for more than 150 years, securing the energy production of the former German Democratic Republic (GDR) and supplying 32,477 million kWh in 2018. Brandenburg's Energy Strategy 2030 envisages lignite as a so-called bridging technology. The extraction of lignite coal and the expansion of wind energy were also seen as two sides of the same coin - the further extraction of lignite coal as a bridging technology could also be politically justified through its pioneering role in the field of wind energy (Interviewee 4). With the coal phase-out decided in 2018, which also means an end to lignite mining in Brandenburg, questions about Brandenburg's 'identity' as an energy region became evident (Interviewee 7). In Brandenburg, there still is a 40 per cent endorsement of the expansion of wind energy according to a IASS survey (Wolf, 2020). Nevertheless, only 6 per cent are content with the implementation of the German energy transition by the federal government. From 2019 onwards, the federal state government recognised that transparency and acceptance are key for future wind energy developments in Brandenburg.

What role has the notion of energy justice and energy sovereignty played in the development of wind energy in Brandenburg?

Acceptance has been a more common term linked to wind energy in Brandenburg rather than justice and sovereignty. For instance, Brandenburg's 2012 energy strategy added a fourth premise to its energy policy: acceptance and participation. Moreover, from 2018, the federal state government increasingly talked about acceptance issues linked to wind energy that needed to be addressed. Acceptance, regional value creation and participation became key terms, including expressions such as socially acceptable expansion. For example, in 2019, a law on the payment of a special levy to municipalities in proximity of newly erected wind turbines was introduced in Brandenburg to increase local acceptance.

Although acceptance and participation have been much-used terms, the notion of justice linked to wind energy has been used by some actors such as academics (such as Eichenauer and Gailing, 2020), political parties, anti-wind energy groups, the Wind Energy Association (BWE) but also increasingly by residents themselves. Topics have been the distributions of burdens linked to the expansion of wind energy such as network charges, expansion rates across the federal states, including the call for equal expansion targets and speeds, unfair and non-transparent planning processes, fairer site selections, more equitable distribution of the benefits of wind energy to achieve greater acceptance at the local level, and justice issue within the overall German energy transition.

Apart from the distribution of costs and benefits, the balancing of interests in decision-making processes has also played an important role over the course of the last few years. For instance, as part of decision-making in regional or land use planning but also regarding differing interests of individual landowners and municipalities. During the past years and especially with the federal legislation in 2022 the principle of an 'overriding public interest' with regards to renewable energy has been introduced. This principle, now legally anchored in §2 of the EEG, will have an impact on decision-making in regional planning and land use planning procedures, granting wind energy privilege over other public or private interests. It can be seen as an expression of a shift in the debate, where justice concerning the interests of general public welfare, but also towards future generations is granted more weight in relation to individual interests.

Overall, justice - albeit not necessarily under this term - has played a role concerning the following dimensions:

Procedural justice

In the past, decisions on where to establish wind parks were made through regional wind plans that identified suitable wind areas. Following the legislative changes in 2022, the focus shifted to now designating wind priority areas. Despite this change, the determination of these areas still rests with the regional assemblies whose members are mayors and municipal leaders as well as a certain number of freely appointed delegates from the districts, serving as the central authority for regional planning. Concerns arose particularly among smaller municipalities. They felt disadvantaged due to their limited involvement in the regional assemblies. Initially, municipalities with fewer than 10,000 residents (later adjusted to 5,000) could merely attend meetings without the right to vote. To some of these smaller municipalities, this exclusion felt unjust given that wind areas tended to be designated around small or isolated settlements, owing to distancing regulations (Interviewee 3). These municipalities successfully lobbied for an expansion of the regional assemblies so now all municipalities regardless of their size are members.

Moreover, municipalities and residents sometimes perceive themselves as disadvantaged due to preliminary negotiations between landowners and investors/project developers, which predefine decisions, rendering further involvement of the community or residents in informal participation partially redundant.

"I'll tell you something: There's a pack of wolves out there and they're scoping out their prey. And those are the landowners. [...] They're looking for land where energy could be permissible. And as soon as there's a certain degree of permissibility, that's when the project

developers, along with their staff, start approaching the landowners. We as municipalities don't actually control which project developer ultimately gets awarded the contract" (Interviewee 5).

Sometimes residents, municipalities and/or other initiatives/organisations feel that formal participation processes are unjust, as their individual interests might not be considered. As one of the interviewees puts it,

"Regional planning tries, of course, to find the broadest possible intersection among vastly different interests. But in the end, there's always some discontent because wind energy is simply a contentious topic where regional planning must decide: Do we lean more towards environmental thinking, or do we lean towards investments and income? Or what do we do? And that's the deliberation, one must indeed opt for one path or the other in the end, and the plan can only have one outcome, not multiple variants. [...] It's just that in the end, not everyone can win when opinions diverge" (Interviewee 3).

Moreover, whether informal participation processes as part of the local planning procedures are perceived as just and therefore are successful in creating acceptance seems to heavily rely on the attitudes, values, experiences, and competencies of the companies involved, as well as on responsible individuals in the municipalities. As there are sometimes very scarce resources within municipalities and little overarching or intermediary structures supporting these processes (only very limited advisory services exist), significant disparities exist in terms of the quality and outcomes of these processes. A member of the Brandenburg parliament describes how the imbalance between the impact on individual municipalities (particularly smaller ones) concerning the number of wind turbines to be installed and their available resources for effective participation systematically impedes informal participation processes,

"Wind power tends to occur where smaller communities are located, simply due to distance regulations and so on. This has implications for a number of things but particularly with regards to approval procedures and participation processes. In these municipalities, there are often individuals assigned to these tasks, who might have ten-tenths of a position which in other communities ten different individuals, each specialised in their field, would handle" (Interviewee 1).

Distributional justice

One of the most pressing issues in terms of distributional justice that has come up in most interviews is the comparatively high electricity prices in Brandenburg. In the northern and eastern German federal states, due to the relatively extensive developments of wind energy, the costs for the required expansion of the power grid are funded by passing on the so-called network charges to consumers through electricity prices. Consequently, the financial burden on consumers in these regions is higher compared to some southern and western German federal states with less wind energy. This disparity is widely regarded as a significant issue concerning the fair distribution of costs and benefits, as one of the Interviewees explains,

"It simply cannot be - and this is understood by everyone - that as a reward for wind energy expansion, the highest electricity prices are to be paid here. And I believe that concerning

this issue of fairness - there are certainly a few other issues too - but this is the most significant and crucial one" (Interviewee 2).

A mayor from one municipality in Brandenburg explains how this directly affects acceptance in practice,

"Why should I agree to the expansion of a wind park or a new wind turbine, resulting in me seeing a higher electricity bill in the end? I'm not crazy!" (Interviewee 5).

Besides the high electricity prices, it is also the (insufficient) opportunities for regional value creation that have shaped the debates around acceptance issues in Brandenburg. A very crucial factor in this context is the financial participation of municipalities, citizens, and property owners in regional value creation through wind energy. The financial participation opportunities have increased due to an introduction of a levy for municipalities that has been enshrined on the federal level in §6 of the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) and on the federal state level in the form of the Wind Energy Plant Levy Law (BbgWindAbgG). For some interviewees this has come with possible changes,

"So, there was a major point of criticism in Brandenburg as well: we didn't benefit from wind energy at all. And through this solution, indeed, that has changed. It has translated into financial gains, and quite attractively so, it must be said" (Interviewee 3).

However, so far this opportunity has been utilised very differently. In practice, it not only appears to depend on whether a company wants to offer a levy but also on the extent to which municipalities are capable of conducting negotiations with companies to receive it, as this description from one of the interviewees illustrates,

"Not a single wind farm operator came forward voluntarily and said, 'Hey, we have wind turbines here, we're producing something. So, we can pay you 0.2 cents per kilowatt-hour. Let's make a contract.' [...] Due to the new legal regulations, I myself contacted all the plant operators: 'Look, there's a new legal regulation here. Shouldn't we sit down together?' Six weeks of silence. Not a single company reached out. Then, I sent a small reminder letter. And then there were two companies that said, 'Yes, we're in, we can do it.' Other companies, one of which operates 16 wind turbines, they said, 'We don't want to pay at all. We don't believe that it generates acceptance,' and that we shouldn't burden the electricity consumer additionally with any costs, right?" (Interviewee 5).

Another factor at play is the relatively limited employment impact of wind energy in contrast to other (exporting) industries. Operating the facilities requires minimal local involvement, and only a handful of companies, like Energiequelle or Enertrag, are genuinely rooted and active employers in the region. In a federal state like Brandenburg, which is affected, for instance, by job losses due to the coal phase-out, this might hinder acceptance for the transition from a coal-based to a renewable energy-oriented region.

Besides high electricity prices and opportunities for regional value creation, another topic is the question of how evenly – or just – wind energy itself is distributed geographically and how this influences the perception of just distribution of costs and benefits.

This, on the one hand, has a nationwide North-South component as significantly more wind energy has developed in the North and East compared to the South and West of Germany.

One of the interviewees explains this unequal distribution of wind energy, pointing towards several interests that need to be balanced,

"I doubt that, in the short term - I can't consider it in the medium and long term - the new regulations will lead to, let's say, a 'fairer' distribution of wind energy use because there are also reasons why companies haven't invested in the South. It won't only be because there are much more landscape protection areas... They exist in North Germany and East Germany as well. But what's here? The land is flat, the wind blows well, and it's more economically viable to invest in the North and the East than in the South. So, for me, it's a question of how do I create incentives to distribute investments more evenly, precisely in the South and the West?" (Interviewee 3).

Moreover, there is also an urban-rural component, as described by one of the interviewees,

"Heading out from the north of Berlin towards Bernau, I think there are three or four turbines. And that's all that currently exists somewhere in Berlin, although there's plenty of space available. [...] However, here, within the same distance of 1 or 2 kilometres, there are one hundred turbines" (Interviewee 4).

Lastly, there is also a difference between smaller and larger municipalities, as due to distance regulations, wind turbines tend to be built around smaller municipalities (see section on procedural justice).

Recognition justice

An important context for understanding the acceptance issues in Brandenburg is linked to, for example, the German reunification and the decline of lignite mining and other industries and later on, the decision of the federal government to phase out coal-fired power generation. Some regions in Brandenburg have been characterised by decades of lignite mining. Lignite mining has been associated with, on one hand, significant environmental destruction and the relocation of entire villages, but on the other hand, the coal industry was one of the largest employers and source of value creation in the region. As a result of the German reunification, the non-competitive coal sector of the former German Democratic Republic (GDR) collapsed and more than 90 per cent of employees lost their jobs (Statistik der Kohlenwirtschaft e.V., 2023). For the people in these regions, changes in the 1990s were often accompanied by sociocultural devaluation, devaluation of work, and status-related downgrading (Gürtler & Herber, 2021). These experiences continue to shape the region today and can affect the willingness to accept and shape other technological changes (Gürtler & Herberg, 2023). Different experiences related to past change processes make it difficult even today to equally acknowledge diverse (sometimes marginalised) perspectives (e.g. people, who have lost their jobs or are in fear of losing them due to the impending changes, people, who have lost their homes due to extractive practices of coal mining, and young people feeling threatened by the climate crisis). When debating a just expansion of wind energy in Brandenburg, these experiences must be considered as an important context.

Also, as a result of historical experiences in the East German federal states since the reunification, some researchers have described a widely held sentiment of people that certain voices are not heard or are misrepresented in public discourses. Looking at discourses surrounding the coal phase-out, Gürtler and Herber (2021) have described how the feeling of lacking recognition fundamentally restricts the acceptance and willingness to

engage in political debates. They consider increasing populist mobilisation and a significant increase in votes for the Alternative for Germany (AfD) as indicators for this lack of engagement. In their study, they have pointed out that current discourses predominantly focus on questions of distributional justice and transition funding, while recognitional justice concerns are often perceived to be absent. This emphasis on distributional justice measures can also be seen with regards to wind energy development in Brandenburg. Moreover, some of the interviewees mentioned that financial participation might not be enough, seeing that some residents have said that “they just want to buy us” (Interviewee 5), demonstrating that the promise of financial compensation cannot always alleviate feelings of lacking recognitional justice. Gürtler and Herbert (2021) conclude in their study that the current emphasis on redistribution linked to the coal phase-out must therefore not come at the expense of recognition and procedural justice issues. The same seems to be relevant for wind energy development.

6 SYNTHESIS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Recommendations for speeding up wind energy developments in Germany and increasing its acceptance have already been drawn up by several researchers over the past years (e.g. acatech et al., 2022; Benita, 2023; Eichenauer & Gailing, 2020; Hirschl et al., 2023; Radtke, 2020; Rosenkranz et al., 2020). In this section, our aim is not to repeat these recommendations in this report, although some of the below recommendations might go along similar themes and directions but rather to list and build on the recommendations mentioned by our interviewees. Moreover, our recommendations are mainly focused on recent developments in wind energy (rather than looking at the past). Our initial list of recommendations was discussed with two of our colleagues, who have extensively worked on wind energy issues in Brandenburg. This section is divided into two themes: a) local value creation and participation and b) governance processes and institutions. Each of these themes is linked to several recommendations. The subsections are structured as follows: first, current challenges are being outlined to provide context to the recommendations and, second, several recommendations are being outlined.

Before reading this section, we felt that it was important to point out some of the historical and cultural background of this region to ground the recommendations within a specific context. Recently, regional value creation has become a key term when discussing possibilities of increasing the acceptance of wind energy. Energy cooperatives (or other ways for municipalities and residents to directly benefit from wind energy) have been considered to be one of the key approaches for increasing regional value creation and have been established in several regions in Germany. Traditionally, the expansion of cooperatives beyond energy was prevalent throughout Germany but faced stagnation in the new federal states during the era of the German Democratic Republic (DDR). As a result, fostering the capacity, norms, and novel traditions necessary for developing energy cooperatives will require time and effort in these regions. Furthermore, differences in income structure and available capital resources persist between the new and old federal states, posing challenges for residents and communities aiming to invest. For instance, inheritance in the new federal states is only half as prevalent as in the old federal states, contributing to substantial wealth disparities between the regions (Tagesschau online, 2023). Considering that wind energy in Brandenburg has mainly been developed through international companies, where income derived from wind energy has not gone to the region, finding ways to enhance regional value creation is key. Nonetheless, this might not be so straightforward if the need to build up cultural, financial and knowledge resources is not being acknowledged. This counts for residents, communities, companies and municipalities in the region.

1) Local value creation and (financial) participation for greater acceptance

Background: In Brandenburg, most of the income generated by wind turbines has not benefited the affected municipalities and residents; instead, it has largely gone to investors and wind energy operators operating at a supra-regional or international level. Furthermore, residents and local businesses in these areas have frequently faced some of the highest electricity prices in Germany. This is largely due to escalating network charges required for expanding the grid to accommodate renewable energy sources. These charges have shown

substantial discrepancies across the various German federal states, with Brandenburg experiencing particularly high rates. Recent targets in wind energy and the necessity to expand the grid have reignited discussions about how network charges are distributed among the federal states. These issues have been identified as significant challenges in addressing the acceptance levels surrounding wind energy in the region. As described by one of the interviewees,

"How do we create regional value? And as comprehensively as possible from production to generation, to storage, to sale. Keep as much as possible here locally and then you also create acceptance, because then there are jobs" (Interviewee 4).

As the case study has shown some of these challenges have been recognised and measures have been put in place, including a levy for municipalities that has been enshrined on the federal level in §6 of the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) and on the federal state level in the form of the Wind Energy Plant Levy Law (BbgWindAbgG). Still, for some of the interviewees these measures and instruments have not gone far enough (Interviewee 1,4,5). Moreover, as of recently, no actual payments have been made as part of this levy in the region, posing difficulties in assessing its impact at this stage (Interviewee 1,3,5). It is generally assumed that the levy is too low to have a significant effect on acceptance in the municipalities and its residents and communities. This has raised several key questions:

- How can regional value creation linked to the expansion of wind energy be enhanced?
- How can the costs and benefits associated with expanding wind energy be equitably distributed among various actors?

Recommendations:

Local value creation: Changes needed in the federal states and its municipalities

- a) **Improving the existing Wind Turbine Levy Law (BbgWindAbgG):** Several interviewees proposed augmenting the current levy (currently set at 10,000 euros per turbine per year) to have a substantial impact on fostering acceptance. Furthermore, an ongoing initiative in the federal state parliament seeks to revise the levy calculation method, suggesting a shift from a fixed per-turbine payment to one based on the megawatt nominal capacity of the turbine. As highlighted by Interviewee 1, "the higher the wind turbine output, the more money flows to the municipality." Considering technological advancements in wind energy, this approach, according to Interviewee 1, increases financial participation opportunities whilst simultaneously creating incentives for wind energy companies to invest in more effective and powerful turbines (Interviewee 1).

Apart from that, a capacity-based levy would be more appropriate for Airborne Wind Energy (AWE) systems. This new technology will be deployed in the years to come in the range of a few 100 kW – a system-based levy at the same level as for established wind turbines would jeopardise the business case of these installations. Within the JustWind4All project a Lab is specifically focusing on how to introduce AWE in Brandenburg in a fair and acceptable way (JW4A report forthcoming).

- b) **Facilitating proactive cooperation between project developers and landowners to increase participatory approaches and enhance local value creation:** The financial benefits that municipalities and residents reap from wind energy often hinge on the willingness of wind turbine developers and operators to incorporate profit-sharing measures into their business strategies. As emphasised by Interviewee 5,

“The expansion of renewable wind energy is a societal challenge, and it must be acknowledged that there is a corporate responsibility linked to social issues. Anyone who builds a wind turbine, or multiple turbines, must be aware that they have also taken on a social responsibility for the region” (Interviewee 5).

Active collaborations between project developers and landowners can foster participation-oriented solutions. This can include models to guarantee a more equitable distribution of income among landowners. One such approach is the implementation of leasing schemes, where the income or rent is distributed on a staggered basis among a pool of owners. Scenarios where only a single landowner benefits from providing land for wind turbines should be prevented, according to some of the interviewees.

- c) **Expanding opportunities for municipalities and citizens to directly benefit financially:** As Hildebrand et al. (2023) have shown the most effective way to increase local value creation effects is the direct participation of citizens and municipalities in wind park investments. Participation in ownership ensures that wind energy operator's profits stay within the local community, granting citizens a meaningful voice in the process (Salecki et al, p. 31). Increasing opportunities for ownership participation therefore is crucial, for example, through creating energy cooperatives or municipal utilities (Interviewee 3). For this to happen, municipalities require resources, capacities and knowledge. This could be achieved by creating an advisory service for energy cooperatives (Interviewee 7). Especially municipalities with fewer resources often lack the financial means to participate in such investment opportunities surrounding ownership participation (Interviewee 4). Options for creating the necessary conditions to enable investments for municipalities include state guarantees and loans (Hirschl et al., 2023, p. 428).

Moreover, interviewees widely agreed that creating energy cost-saving models for citizens, such as offering locally generated energy at a discounted rate (referred to as citizens' energy (Bürgerstrom)), holds significant promise for the acceptance of wind energy. This approach has the advantages of expanding wind energy and its benefits in a "visible and tangible" way for residents and households in the affected regions (Interviewee 1).

- d) **Support for regionally based companies and municipal enterprises:** In general, promoting the integration of locally based companies and municipal enterprises at each stage such as planning, assembly, and operation of wind turbines can contribute to retaining corporate profits within the region and achieving higher rates of employment (Interviewees 4, 6).

Local value creation: Changes needed at the federal level

- a) **Amendment of the Renewable Energy Act (EEG), paragraph 6:** At the federal level, one of the interviewees proposed amending paragraph 6 EEG to make the offer of financial participation mandatory and to earmark funds for specific purposes in the municipality (Interviewee 5).
- b) **Changes to network charges:** A more equitable network charge system is among the most frequently requested fields of action raised by the interviewees to achieve a fairer distribution of costs and benefits linked to the expansion of wind energy (Interviewees 1, 2, 4, 5). Such charges have been a recurring topic of discussion in the political discourse for years, as a change in the network charges linked to grid expansions represents a major challenge. Current proposals range from standardising network charges nationwide to suggestions for establishing different electricity price zones (Interviewee 1).

2) Governance processes and institutions

Background: In 2022, Brandenburg underwent a significant shift in its regional planning system, transitioning from an exclusionary approach utilising ‘wind suitability areas’ to an offer-based planning system featuring ‘wind priority areas’, as mandated by federal law (Onshore Wind Energy Act (WaLG)). In the past, planning communities in Brandenburg were responsible for devising regional plans that focused on concentrating wind energy in specific areas (known as concentration planning) while protecting other areas from wind energy developments. There was a strong commitment from all municipalities, regardless of their stance—whether supportive or resistant towards wind energy—to participate in regional planning. Municipalities were represented in the regional assembly, the primary body responsible for deciding on regional wind plans, ensuring their involvement in determining appropriate wind energy locations. After the legal changes following the federal Onshore Wind Energy Act (WaLG), regional planning communities are now mandated to identify 'wind priority areas' where wind energy takes precedence over other interests. Although areas can no longer be formally excluded from wind energy, the exclusion effect (Ausschlusswirkung) of regional plans continues to hold sway as long as prescribed area targets (2 percent) are fulfilled.

Consequently, a situation arose where there are – apart from still existing limitations associated with nature conservation areas or requirements related to species protection – currently no regional planning restrictions in place for expanding wind energy. To comply with legal mandates, the regional planning communities first need to craft new regional plans, a process potentially spanning several years (Interviewees 1, 3). With the impending 2024 regional and local elections, the reconstitution of the regional assembly (comprising mayors or local officials) could moreover lead to shifts in interests and potential conflicts, prolonging the process even further (Interviewee 7). As long as no drafts of these regional plans exist, Brandenburg is confronted with a transitional phase characterised by several uncertainties, especially with regards to two aspects:

- The absence of draft plans makes it impossible to gauge if the 2 percent area requirement can be met (MWAE Brandenburg, 2023a), leaving uncertainties about whether the regional plans will actually wield any exclusionary effect and whether distancing rules can be kept in place.
- Amid this transitional period without regional plans, there exists the so-called 'privilege in outdoor areas' (Privilegierung im Außenbereich), allowing investors or

project developers, in theory, to seek approval for erecting wind turbines anywhere. Although such possibilities exist, current observations do not support this from happening (Interviewee 1,3). Nevertheless, such possibilities have amplified a narrative within some communities and among residents, fostering the perception of a 'wild west' scenario unfolding concerning wind energy (Interviewee 1, 4, 5).

This situation of uncertainty might trigger resistance against further expansion of wind energy. Moreover, some municipalities feel that with the new planning system, they now have lost decision-making competencies (Interviewee 5).

Furthermore, there is a lack in resources (such as shortage of staff) that still hinder wind energy expansion, especially with regards to informal participation processes during the planning phase but also with regard to permitting processes. Regarding the latter, existing federal and federal state legislation has primarily addressed and expedited planning processes, but not approval and permitting processes. Significant issues persist in this area, particularly concerning the severe shortage of skilled professionals within the relevant permitting authorities (Interviewees 2, 7). Regarding informal participation processes, municipalities themselves often lack the resources and competencies to accompany and proactively shape informal participation processes.

Recommendations:

- a) Addressing uncertainties linked to the absence of regional plans:** The existing uncertainties surrounding regional planning might fuel resistance against wind energy, intensifying 'wild west' narratives among specific groups such as residents and municipalities (Interviewee 5). While these uncertainties might not be easily rectified through legislation (federal legislation provides clear guidelines in this regard), addressing them communicatively is crucial (Interviewee 7). An initial evaluation of how the practices of wind energy developers have changed post-legislative alterations does not seem to support the narrative of unchecked expansion. Additionally, interviewees from an energy company did not consider this an imminent strategy for developers (Interviewee 6). It might be imperative to address 'wild west' narratives to prevent their proliferation.
- b) Addressing the permitting process:** As mentioned by all interviewees, a significant challenge persists in the issue of lengthy approval procedures. According to Interviewee 6, there is a need to digitalise permitting and approval processes and the provision of sufficient staffing to do so. Further suggestions for speeding up approval procedures include legal adjustments at the federal level with the objective of establishing uniform standards and procedures together with other regional planning authorities. This applies in particular to environmental impact assessments, nature and species conservation and heritage protection (Interviewee 2, 6).
- c) Strategically addressing geographic distribution of wind energy:** The federal government's extension of land use targets for individual federal states introduces new challenges related to the criteria-based allocation of these targets to various planning regions and the development of previously untapped land. A commonly articulated objective is to transition from concentration zones to a more evenly distributed system where wind parks are more strategically located so there is a fairer

distribution of costs (in terms of how many wind turbines are surrounding a municipality) and benefits (who gets to financially benefit from wind energy) (Interviewee 7). Therefore, there should be political consideration on how to prevent concentrations in specific areas and promote a more equitable distribution.

Another ongoing discussion in Brandenburg involves the exploration of building wind energy on past opencast mining sites. For this initiative to contribute to a just acceleration of wind energy, it is considered crucial to prevent a continuation of projects by current mine operators by establishing conditions for land transfer to municipal ownership. Ensuring financial participation is also imperative and key to achieving regional value creation (Interviewee 7).

d) Addressing lack of capacities and resources at different levels: A major obstacle to the acceleration of planning processes is a lack of skilled workers in planning, permitting, and approving, but also in the fields of administration especially within smaller municipalities, making it hard for them to successfully navigate cooperation with wind energy developers and carry out informal participation processes (Interviewee 1,4,6). To support companies and municipalities, the federal state of Brandenburg, in 2018, established a consultation centre to mediate potential conflicts and interest in wind energy projects, but capacities are rather limited. Moreover, despite numerous guidelines for 'good' participation, their impacts have been limited, highlighting a need for intermediary structures to facilitate knowledge exchange (Interviewee 1). Measures to enhance empowerment and capacity-building therefore should address the expansion of advisory structures and support services to provide targeted and easily comprehensible information about participation opportunities and value creation effects.

Moreover, empowerment and capacity building should also translate into addressing the shortage in skilled workers in the wind industry at all levels (Interviewee 6). Possible measures encompass enhancing the attractiveness of professions in the field through, for example, salary increases and intensifying and adapting training and further education programs to the technological requirements of the energy transition (Interviewee 6). As a former lignite mining region, the initiation of re-training/requalification initiatives for employees affected by structural change is also considered relevant (Hirschl et al. 2022, Interviewee 6).

e) Adopting the climate plan in Brandenburg: Delays have impeded the adoption of the climate plan in Brandenburg. The failure to secure approval by the end of the current legislative period increases the likelihood of the plan being cancelled or adapted with a new election coming up in 2024. This underscores the imperative to expedite cabinet decisions. Furthermore, the comprehensive implementation of the expert group's far-reaching recommendations for wind energy should be fully taken into account.

REFERENCES

- acatech, Leopoldina, & Akademienunion. (2022). *Wie kann der Ausbau von Photovoltaik und Windenergie beschleunigt werden? Stellungnahme* [Schriftenreihe zur wissenschaftsbasierten Politikberatung]. https://www.leopoldina.org/fileadmin/redaktion/Publikationen/Nationale_Empfehlungen/2022_ESYS-Stellungnahme_Photovoltaik_und_Windenergie.pdf
- AEE. (2010). *Energie-Kommune des Monats: Mühlenfließ-Schlalach*. <https://www.unendlich-viel-energie.de/die-agentur/projekte/energie-kommunen/energie-kommune-des-monats-muehlenfliess-schlalach>
- AEE. (2022). *Umfrage: Wunsch nach Versorgungssicherheit beflügelt Akzeptanz von Erneuerbaren Energien* [Pressemitteilung]. Agentur für Erneuerbare Energien. <https://www.unendlich-viel-energie.de/umfrage-wunsch-nach-versorgungssicherheit-befluegelt-akzeptanz-von-erneuerbaren-energien>
- Agora Energiewende. (2015). *Understanding the Energiewende. FAQ on the ongoing transition of the German power system*. https://www.agora-energiewende.de/fileadmin/Projekte/2015/Understanding_the_EW/Agora_Understanding_the_Energiewende.pdf
- Appunn, K., Haas, Y., & Wettengel, J. (2023). *Germany's energy consumption and power mix in charts* [Factsheet]. Clean Energy Wire. <https://www.cleanenergywire.org/factsheets/germanys-energy-consumption-and-power-mix-charts>
- Arzt, I. (2012, November 29). Windräder drehen sich vergeblich; Energie Immer öfter kann erneuerbarer Strom nicht eingespeist werden, weil die Stromnetze fehlen. *Taz*. <https://advance.lexis.com/document?crd=cd76df64-52f7-4b37-939c-2618e36a34c5&pdocfullpath=%2Fshared%2Fdocument%2Fnews%2Furn%3AcontentItem%3A5751-K8M1-F117-G158-00000-00&pdsourcingtype=&pdcontentcomponentid=158474&pdmfid=1519360&pdisurlapi=true>
- Benita, G. (2023). *Vom Winde verdreht? Mediale Narrative über Windkraft, Naturschutz und Energiewandel* [Working Paper]. Otto Brenner Stiftung. <https://www.otto-brenner-stiftung.de/vom-winde-verdreht/>
- Berliner Zeitung. (2002, August 15). *Die Schattenseite des Windkraft-Booms Windenergie hat Konjunktur. Doch Bürgerinitiativen und Gerichte machen die Suche nach neuen Standorten immer schwieriger*. <https://advance.lexis.com/document?crd=94dc7440-e0d1-4bdf-9da7-1de7d699aa3a&pdocfullpath=%2Fshared%2Fdocument%2Fnews%2Furn%3AcontentItem%3A4G9S-00T0-TWX2-828W-00000-00&pdsourcingtype=&pdcontentcomponentid=284350&pdmfid=1519360&pdisurlapi=true>
- BMUV. (2022). *Bundeskabinett beschleunigt naturverträglichen Windkraft-Ausbau deutlich* (Press Release Pressemitteilung Nr. 074/22). BMUV. <https://www.bmuv.de/pressemitteilung/bundeskabinett-beschleunigt-naturvertraeglichen-windkraft-ausbau-deutlich>
- BMWK. (2015). *Cost-effective, plannable and market-focused: The 2014 EEG reform* [Newsletter]. BMWK Energiewende direkt. <https://www.bmwk-energiewende.de/EWD/Redaktion/EN/Newsletter/2015/01/Meldung/eeg-reform.html>

- BMWK. (2022a). *Das steckt im Osterpaket* [Newsletter]. BMWK Energiewende direkt. <https://www.bmwk-energiewende.de/EWD/Redaktion/Newsletter/2022/04/Meldung/topthema.html>
- BMWK. (2022b). *Habeck: „Das Osterpaket ist der Beschleuniger für die erneuerbaren Energien“* [Pressemitteilung]. Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz (BMWK). <https://www.bmwk.de/Redaktion/DE/Pressemitteilungen/2022/04/20220406-habeck-das-osterpaket-ist-der-beschleuniger-fur-die-erneuerbaren-energien.html>
- BMWK. (2022c). Überblickspapier Osterpaket. *Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz*. https://www.bmwk.de/Redaktion/DE/Downloads/Energie/0406_ueberblickspapier_osterpaket.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=1
- BMWSB. (2023). *Gesetz zur Erhöhung und Beschleunigung des Ausbaus von Windenergieanlagen an Land (sog. Wind-an-Land-Gesetz)* [Legislative procedure]. Bundesministerium für Wohnen, Stadtentwicklung und Bauwesen. <https://www.bmwsb.bund.de/SharedDocs/gesetzgebungsverfahren/Webs/BMWSB/DE/ExterneLinks/wind-an-land-gesetz.html>
- Bons, M., Jakob, M., Sach, T., Pape, Dr. C., Zink, C., Geiger, D., Wegner, Dr. N., Boinsky, O., Benz, S., & Kahles, Dr. M. (2023). *Flächenverfügbarkeit und Flächenbedarfe für den Ausbau der Windenergie an Land* (Final Report 32(2023; Climate Change, p. 140). German Federal Environment Agency. Klicken, um Alternative zu verwenden. <https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/publikationen/flaechenverfuegbarkeit-flaechenbedarfe-fuer-den>
- Bovet, J. (2015). Steuerung der Windenergie durch Raumordnung. Aktuelle Rechtsprechung als Herausforderung für die Planung. *Informationen zur Raumentwicklung, Heft 6/2015*, 591–602.
- Bues, A. (2018). Planning, Protest, and Contentious Politics: The Governance of Wind Energy in Brandenburg and Ontario. *disP - The Planning Review*, 54(4), 34–45. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02513625.2018.1562796>
- Bundesregierung. (2022, Dezember). *EEG 2023: „We’re tripling the speed of the expansion of renewable energies“*. <https://www.bundesregierung.de/breg-de/schwerpunkte/klimaschutz/amendment-of-the-renewables-act-2060448>
- Bundesregierung. (2023, February 1). *„Wind-an-Land-Gesetz“: Mehr Windenergie für Deutschland*. <https://www.bundesregierung.de/breg-de/schwerpunkte/klimaschutz/wind-an-land-gesetz-2052764#:~:text=Verbindliche%20Fl%C3%A4chenziele%20f%C3%BCr%20Bundesl%C3%A4nder,am%20selben%20Standort%20sind%20vorzuziehen.>
- Bündnis Bürgerenergie e.V. (2022, July 7). Fortschritte und vertane Chancen im EEG 2023. *Bündnis Bürgerenergie e.V.* <https://www.buendnis-buergerenergie.de/aktuelles/news/artikel/2022-7-7/fortschritte-und-vertane-chancen-im-eeg-2023>
- Bündnis für Bernau. (2018). *Bernauer Erklärung gegen ungebremste Windkraftnutzung*. <https://www.buendnis-fuer-bernaue.de/project/windkraftnutzung/>
- Bunzel, K., Bovet, J., Thrän, D., & Eichhorn, M. (2019). Hidden outlaws in the forest? A legal and spatial analysis of onshore wind energy in Germany. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 55, 14–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2019.04.009>
- Büüsker, A.-K. (2022, March 24). Die Bedeutung von Gas für die deutsche Energieversorgung. *Deutschlandfunk*. <https://www.deutschlandfunk.de/energieversorgung-russland-deutschland-100.html>

- BWE. (2018). *Windenergieausbau nicht ersticken – Privilegierung von Windenergieanlagen im Planungsrecht wichtig für Klimaschutz und Strukturwandel* [Pressemitteilung]. Bundesverband WindEnergie. <https://www.windenergie.de/presse/pressemitteilungen/detail/windenergieausbau-nicht-ersticken-privilegierung-von-windenergieanlagen-im-planungsrecht-wichtig-f/>
- BWE. (2021a). *Brandenburg steht bei Regionalplanung vor Scherbenhaufen—Windverband fordert Neustart* [Pressemitteilung]. Windmesse. <https://w3.windmesse.de/windenergie/pm/38899-bwe-berlin-brandenburg-verband-landesverband-teilregionalplan-oderland-spree-unwirksam-neustart-scherbenhaufen-rechtswidrig>
- BWE. (2022). *Windenergie: Brandenburg lehnt Bundesgesetz zu Abständen ab* [Pressemitteilung]. Windmesse. <https://w3.windmesse.de/windenergie/pm/40750-bwe-berlin-brandenburg-abstandsregelung-mindestabstand-wohnbebauung-windkraftanlage-windpark-bundesgesetz-landesregierung>
- BWE. (2019). *Landesplanung*. <https://www.wind-energie.de/verband/lvs/berlin-brandenburg/landesplanung/#:~:text=Am%201.,%2DMoratorium%E2%80%9C%20in%20Kraft%20getreten.>
- BWE. (2021b, December 31). *Die deutschen Bundesländer im Vergleich. Die Bundesländer in Zahlen*. <https://www.wind-energie.de/themen/zahlen-und-fakten/bundeslaender/>
- BWE. (2023). *Jahrbuch Windenergie 2023/2024*. <https://www.windenergie.de/service/shop/artikel-detail/jahrbuch-windenergie-20232024/>
- Colell, Dr. A., Knodt, Prof. Dr. M., Stoll, P., Kemmerzell, Dr. J., Reitz, S., Goshen, L., & Ohlhorst, Dr. D. (2022). Hintergrund: Konflikte und Akteure – Gesellschaftliche Herausforderungen bei der Umsetzung der Stromwende. Ariadne Hintergrund. *Kopernikus-Projekt Ariadne Potsdam-Institut Für Klimafolgenforschung (PIK)*. https://ariadneprojekt.de/media/2022/01/Ariadne-Hintegrund_Konflikte_und_Akteure_Januar2022.pdf
- Dehmer, D. (2013). The German Energiewende: The First Year. *The Electricity Journal*, 26(1), 71–78. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tej.2012.12.001>
- Der Spiegel. (2000, January 30). Der Osten ist grün. *Der Spiegel*. <https://www.spiegel.de/politik/der-osten-ist-gruen-a-e1605165-0002-0001-0000-000015561266>
- Deutscher Bundestag, Online-Dienste (Ed.). (2022). *Osterpaket zum Ausbau erneuerbarer Energien beschlossen*. <https://www.bundestag.de/dokumente/textarchiv/2022/kw27-de-energie-902620>
- Eichenauer, E. (2016). *Im Gegenwind. Lokaler Widerstand gegen den Bau von Windkraftanlagen in Brandenburg. Ergebnisse einer Onlinebefragung*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.29464.39685>
- Eichenauer, E., & Gailing, L. (2020). *Gute Bedingungen für lokale Wertschöpfung aus Windkraftanlagen. Erfahrungen und Empfehlungen* (IRS Dialog Policy Papers) [Policy Paper]. Leibniz-Institut für Raumbezogene Sozialforschung (IRS). https://leibniz-irs.de/fileadmin/user_upload/IRS_Dialog_Transferpublikationen/IRS_Dialog_Gute_Bedingungen_Wertschoepfung_Windkraftanlagen.pdf
- Eichenauer, E., Reusswig, F., Meyer-Ohlendorf, L., & Lass, W. (2018). Bürgerinitiativen gegen Windkraftanlagen und der Aufschwung rechtspopulistischer Bewegungen. In O. Kühne & F. Weber (Eds.), *Bausteine der Energiewende* (pp. 633–651). Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-658-19509-0_32
- Ermisch, M., Margarita, I., Kaiser, K., Packroff, J., Wedell, P., & Zipf, C. (2018). *Gemeinsam gewinnen – Windenergie vor Ort. Ein Grundlagenpapier zu den Themen*

- Wertschöpfung, Bürgerbeteiligung und Akzeptanz* [Grundlagenpapier]. Bundesverband WindEnergie e. V. (BWE). https://www.windenergie.de/fileadmin/redaktion/dokumente/publikationen-oeffentlich/themen/01-mensch-und-umwelt/01-windkraft-vor-ort/20180614_gemeinsam_gewinnen_windenergie_vor_ort_web.pdf
- Fabra, P. N., Matthes, D. F. C., & Newbery, P. D. (2015). The energy transition in Europe: Initial lessons from Germany, the UK and France. *Centre on Regulation in Europe (Cerre)*, 152.
- Fachagentur Windenergie an Land. (2023). *Brandenburg (BB)*. Länderinformationen Zur Windenergie. <https://www.fachagentur-windenergie.de/veroeffentlichungen/laenderinformationen/laenderinformationen-zur-windenergie/brandenburg/>
- Frese, A. (2013, May 13). Wirtschaftsminister Christoffers im Interview: „Der Osten zahlt zu hohe Strompreise“. *Tagespiegel*. <https://www.tagesspiegel.de/wirtschaft/der-osten-zahlt-zu-hohe-strompreise-2360005.html>
- Gailing, L., Bues, A., Kern, K., & Röhring, A. (2019). Socio-spatial dimensions in energy transitions: Applying the TPSN framework to case studies in Germany. *Environment and Planning A: Economy and Space*, 52(6), 1112–1130. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0308518X19845142>
- Geels, F. W. (2020). *Transformative innovation and socio-technical transitions to address grand challenges* [Working Paper]. European Commission. <https://euagenda.eu/upload/publications/transformative-innovation-and-socio-technical-transitions-to-address-grand-challenges.pdf>
- Gläser, H. (1998, August 15). Boom trotz Unsicherheiten. *Taz*. <https://taz.de/!1330299/>
- Guan, J. (2020). Westerly breezes and easterly gales: A comparison of legal, policy and planning regimes governing onshore wind in Germany and China. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 67, 101506. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101506>
- Gürtler, K., & Herberg, J. (2023). Moral rifts in the coal phase-out—How mayors shape distributive and recognition-based dimensions of a just transition in Lusatia. *Journal of Environmental Policy & Planning*, 25(2), 194–209. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2021.1992267>
- Haan, P., & Simmler, M. (2018). Wind electricity subsidies — A windfall for landowners? Evidence from a feed-in tariff in Germany. *Journal of Public Economics*, 159, 16–32. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpubeco.2018.01.011>
- Hackenbruch, F. (2018). Energiewende in der Hauptstadtregion: Darum zahlt Brandenburg weiterhin den höchsten Strompreis. *Tagesspiegel*. <https://www.tagesspiegel.de/berlin/darum-zahlt-brandenburg-weiterhin-den-hoehsten-strompreis-8431654.html>
- Hasse, C. (2022). *Bürgerenergiegesellschaften im EEG 2023*. Bundesverband Windenergie. https://www.wind-energie.de/fileadmin/redaktion/dokumente/publikationen-oeffentlich/themen/04-politische-arbeit/01-gesetzgebung/20220920_Informationspapier_Buergerenergiegesellschaften_im_EEG_2023.pdf
- Hewel, A. B. (2022, December 6). Brandenburg will an deutlich mehr Orten neue Windkraftanlagen ermöglichen. *RBB* 24. <https://www.rbb24.de/politik/beitrag/2022/12/brandenburg-windenergie-ausbau-windraeder-.html>
- Hildebrand, J., Jahnel, V., Rau, I., & Salecki, S. (2023). *Die Energiewende in Kommunen. Zusammenhänge von regionaler Wertschöpfung, lokaler Akzeptanz und finanzieller*

- Beteiligung.* https://www.unendlich-viel-energie.de/media/file/5141.AEE_Renews_Spezial_92_ReWA.pdf
- Hirschl, B., Torliene, L., Schwarz, U., Dunkelberg, E., Weiß, J., Katner, Jannes, Hirschberg, Raoul, Schirok, J., Weyer, G., Wagner, K., Kenneweg, H., Bluhm, H., & Bode, A. (2023). *Gutachten zum Klimaplan Brandenburg* [Endbericht. Im Auftrag des Ministeriums für Landwirtschaft, Umwelt und Klimaschutz des Landes Brandenburg]. Ministerium für Landwirtschaft, Umwelt und Klimaschutz (MLUK). <https://mluk.brandenburg.de/sixcms/media.php/9/Endbericht-Gutachten-Klimaplan-BB.pdf>
- Höppner, Y., & Anker, J. (2019, February 23). Windkraft: Mehr Einfluss und Informationen für Bürger. *Berliner Morgenpost*. <https://www.morgenpost.de/brandenburg/article216506207/Windkraft-Mehr-Einfluss-und-Informationen-fuer-Buerger.html>
- Hornig, F., & Dohmen, F. (2004, March 29). Die große Luftnummer. *Der Spiegel*. <https://magazin.spiegel.de/EpubDelivery/spiegel/pdf/30346813>
- IRENA. (2013). *30 Years of Policies for Wind Energy. Lessons from 12 Wind Energy Market*. https://www.irena.org/-/media/Files/IRENA/Agency/Publication/2013/GWEC_WindReport_All_web-display.pdf?rev=9d4b2fa3873a442b88ea686d0ccb20e3
- Jacobsson, S., & Lauber, V. (2006). The politics and policy of energy system transformation— Explaining the German diffusion of renewable energy technology. *Energy Policy*, 34(3), 256–276. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2004.08.029>
- Kerres, P., Sieler, R. E., Naarita, J., Eckhardt, J., & Overbeck, L. (2020). *Germany's policy practices for improving community acceptance of wind farms*. adelphi. <https://adelphi.de/de/publikationen/germanys-policy-practices-for-improving-community-acceptance-of-wind-farms>
- KNE. (2019). *Moratorium für die Genehmigung von Windenergieanlagen in Brandenburg. "KNE-Wortmeldung"* [Positionspapier]. Kompetenzzentrum Naturschutz und Energiewende KNE gGmbH. https://www.naturschutz-energiewende.de/wp-content/uploads/KNE-Wortmeldung_Moratorium-f%C3%BCr-die-Genehmigung-von-Windenergieanlagen-in-Brandenburg.pdf
- Kübler, K. (2018). Der lange Schatten des Energiekonzepts 2010 und die nächste Etappe der Energiewende. *Energiewirtschaftliche Tagesfragen*, 68 Jg. (2018)(Heft 11).
- Leiren, M. D., & Reimer, I. (2018). Historical institutionalist perspective on the shift from feed-in tariffs towards auctioning in German renewable energy policy. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 43, 33–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2018.05.022>
- Liuzzo, D. (2006). *Deutschland Lage von Brandenburg*. Wikipedia Commons. https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Deutschland_Lage_von_Brandenburg.svg
- Local Energy Consulting. (2020). *Akzeptanz und lokale Teilhabe in der Energiewende. Handlungsempfehlungen für eine umfassende Akzeptanzpolitik*. Impuls im Auftrag von Agora Energiewende. https://static.agora-energiewende.de/fileadmin/Projekte/2020/2020_07_EE-Akzeptanz/182_A-EW_Akzeptanz-Energiewende_WEB.pdf
- Locke, M. (2016, June 13). Windrad ohne Schwung; In diesem Jahr wurden in Brandenburg weniger Anlagen errichtet als geplant. *Berliner Zeitung*. <https://advance.lexis.com/document?crd=85b1fb4b-faae-44a6-806b-a130343dfd7b&pddocfullpath=%2Fshared%2Fdocument%2Fnews%2Furn%3AcontentItem%3A5K0N-P0D1-JC3P-01B4-00000-00&pdsourcingtype=&pdccontentcomponentid=284350&pdmfid=1519360&pdisurlapi=true>

- Maischberger (Director). (2022, February 23). 'Es geht um die nationale Sicherheit'—*Wirtschaftsminister Robert Habeck* [Maischberger. Die Woche]. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=81DaRPwkXZs>
- Meister, T., Schmid, B., Seidl, I., & Klagge, B. (2020). How municipalities support energy cooperatives: Survey results from Germany and Switzerland. *Energy, Sustainability and Society*, 10(1), 18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13705-020-00248-3>
- Metzner, T. (2012, January 2). Ausblick: Was Brandenburg im Jahr 2012 erwartet. *Tagespiegel*. <https://www.tagesspiegel.de/berlin/was-brandenburg-im-jahr-2012-erwartet-7005676.html>
- Meya, J. N., Neetzow, P., Neubauer, L., & Pechan, A. (2016). Die Menge macht's? Das EEG 2017 und die Folgen für die deutsche Energiewende. *Energiewirtschaftliche Tagesfragen*, 66(11), 34–37.
- MIL Brandenburg. (2023). *Windkraftausbau in Brandenburg kommt voran: Neues Flächenzielgesetz in Kraft* [Pressemitteilung]. Ministerium für Infrastruktur und Landesplanung (MIL). <https://mil.brandenburg.de/mil/de/presse/detail/~03-03-2023-flaechenzielgesetz-windkraftausbau>
- MLUK Brandenburg. (2023). *Klimaplan Brandenburg*. <https://mluk.brandenburg.de/mluk/de/klimaschutz/klimaschutz/klimaplan/>
- Morris, C., & Jungjohann, A. (2016). *Energy Democracy. Germany's Energiewende to Renewables*. Springer International Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-31891-2>
- Moss, T., Becker, S., & Naumann, M. (2015). Whose energy transition is it, anyway? Organisation and ownership of the Energiewende in villages, cities and regions. *Local Environment*, 20(12), 1547–1563. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13549839.2014.915799>
- Müller, D. K., & Morton, P. T. (2021a). *Briefing Report: Wind and Solar Projects in Brandenburg* (Decarbonising Electricity) [Interim Report]. Centre for Interdisciplinary Regional Studies Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, Centre for Climate Justice University of Technology Sydney. https://decarbenergy.net/wp-content/uploads/2021/08/Germany-Working-paper-brandenburg_report_final_en.pdf
- Müller, D. K., & Morton, P. T. (2021b). The space, the time, and the money. Wind energy politics in East Germany. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 40, 62–72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2021.06.001>
- MWAE Brandenburg. (2022). *Energiestrategie 2040*. Ministerium für Wirtschaft, Arbeit und Energie (MWAE). <https://mwae.brandenburg.de/media/bb1.a.3814.de/Energiestrategie2040.pdf>
- MWAE Brandenburg. (2023a). *Länderbericht zum Stand des Ausbaus der erneuerbaren Energien sowie zu Flächen, Planungen und Genehmigungen für die Windenergienutzung an Land*. https://energieportal-brandenburg.de/cms/fileadmin/medien/publikation/laenderbericht_brandenburg_2023_zum_stand_des_ausbaus_der_erneuerbaren_energien_sowie_zu_flaechen__planungen_und_genehmigungen_fuer_die_windenergienutzung_an_land.pdf
- MWAE Brandenburg. (2023b). *Windenergie*. <https://mwae.brandenburg.de/de/windenergie/bb1.c.478387.de>
- NABU Brandenburg, & BUND Brandenburg. (2016). *Gemeinsame Position von NABU und BUND Brandenburg zur Windkraftnutzung*. <https://brandenburg.nabu.de/imperia/md/nabu/images/umwelt/energie/energietraeger/windkraft/20160411-positionspapier-windkraftnutzung-in-brandenburg-bund-nabu-brandenburg.pdf>

- Neller, M. (2012, May 27). Gegen den Wind. *Welt Am Sonntag*. <https://www.welt.de/print/wams/article106382048/Gegen-den-Wind.html>
- Nikionok-Ehrlich, A. (2013, September 2). Wertschöpfung für Kommunen durch Erneuerbare. *Energie & Management*. <https://advance.lexis.com/document?crd=c56b0317-5ef3-4745-9aef-e20753217a48&pddocfullpath=%2Fshared%2Fdocument%2Fnews%2Furn%3Acontentitem%3A5989-DBM1-DY25-C2HS-00000-00&pdsourcgroupingtype=&pdcontentcomponentid=264238&pdmfid=1519360&pdisurlapi=true>
- Osberghaus, H. (1996). Was schert mich mein Wind von gestern. *Taz*, 4816. <https://taz.de/!1477798/>
- Overwien, P., & Groenewald, U. (2015). Viel Wind um den Wind. Aktuelle Herausforderungen für die Regionalplanung in Brandenburg. *Informationen zur Raumentwicklung, Heft 6/2015*, 603–618.
- Pankower Allgemeine Zeitung. (2019, Mai). 270 Bürgermeister & Ortsvorsteher fordern Umsteuern bei Windkraftausbau. *Pankower Allgemeine Zeitung*. <https://www.pankower-allgemeine-zeitung.de/270-buergermeister-ortsvorsteher-fordern-umsteuern-bei-windkraftausbau/>
- Paul, F. C. (2018). Deep entanglements: History, space and (energy) struggle in the German Energiewende. *Geoforum*, 91, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2018.02.017>
- Quentin, J., & Endell, Dr. M. (2020). *EEG 2017: Ausschreibungsspezifische Regelungen für Windenergieanlagen an Land*. Fachagentur Windenergie an Land. https://www.fachagentur-windenergie.de/fileadmin/files/Veroeffentlichungen/FA_Wind_EEG-2017_Ausschreibungen_5Auf_2020.pdf
- Radtke, J. (2020). Das Jahrhundertprojekt der Nachhaltigkeit am Scheideweg: Wie kann die Energiewende in Deutschland breite gesellschaftliche Unterstützung finden? *Zeitschrift für Politikwissenschaft*, 30(1), 97–111. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41358-020-00215-6>
- RBB24. (2020, June 17). Landtag fordert eigenen Klimaplan für Brandenburg. *RBB 24*. <https://www.rbb24.de/studiocottbus/politik/2020/06/brandenburg-landtag-aufstellung-klimaplan.html>
- Regionales Energiemanagement Brandenburg. (2023). *Die Planungsregionen in Brandenburg*. <https://www.energiemanagement-brandenburg.de/regionen.html>
- Reimer, J., & Rößler, N. (2023, June 13). Altmaier stellt sich gegen EU-Vorhaben. *Deutschlandfunk*. <https://www.deutschlandfunk.de/erneuerbare-energien-altmaier-stellt-sich-gegen-eu-vorhaben-100.html>
- Reitz, S., Goshen, L., & Ohlhorst, D. (2022). Trade-offs in German wind energy expansion: Building bridges between different interests, values and priorities. *Energy, Sustainability and Society*, 12(1), 39. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13705-022-00365-1>
- Rettet die Uckermark (RdU). (n.d.). *Wir an Sie*. http://rettet-die-uckermark.de/html/wir_an_sie.html
- Reuswig, F., Braun, F., Eichenauer, E., Fahrenkrug, K., Franzke, J., Heger, I., Ludewig, T., Melzer, M., Ott, K., & Teike Scheepmaker. (2016). *Energiekonflikte. Akzeptanzkriterien und Gerechtigkeitsvorstellungen in der Energiewende. Kernergebnisse und Handlungsempfehlungen eines interdisziplinären Forschungsprojektes*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.30920.72968>
- Reuswig, F., Braun, F., Heger, I., Ludewig, T., Eichenauer, E., & Lass, W. (2016). Against the wind: Local opposition to the German Energiewende. *Utilities Policy*, 41, 214–227. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jup.2016.02.006>

- Rosenkranz, Dr. B., Schäfer, M., & Graichen, Dr. P. (2020). *Sofortprogramm Windenergie an Land. Was jetzt zu tun ist, um die Blockaden zu überwinden*. Agora Energiewende. https://static.agora-energiewende.de/fileadmin/Projekte/2020/2020-01_DE-RE-Boost-2030/A-EW_198_OnshoreSofort_WEB.pdf
- Salecki, Dr. S., Heinbach, K., Hirschl, Prof. Dr. B., Weidinger, R., Schäfer-Stradowsky, S., Ott, R., Lehnert, Dr. W., Kliem, C., Altrock, D. M., Umlauf, D. F., Puffe, M., Seiß, H., Yilmaz, Y., & Kahle, L. (2020). *Finanzielle Beteiligung von betroffenen Kommunen bei Planung, Bau und Betrieb von erneuerbaren Energieanlagen (FinBEE). Ergebnisse für die Windenergie* [Forschungsbereich im Auftrag des Bundesministeriums für Wirtschaft und Energie (BMWi)]. Institut für ökologische Wirtschaftsforschung (IÖW) | Institut für Klimaschutz, Energie und Mobilität (IKEM) | Becker, Büttner, Held PartGmbH (BBH) | Becker Büttner Held Consulting AG (BBHC).
- Schroeter, S. (2011, May 27). Bundesweiter Ausgleich für Netzkosten des Ökostroms. *VDI Nachrichten*. <https://advance.lexis.com/document?crd=771edb44-c6a2-4797-a6bd-59f1468094ca&pddocfullpath=%2Fshared%2Fdocument%2Fnews%2Furn%3Acontentitem%3A58F7-6DF1-JB76-S2VG-00000-00&pdsourcingtype=&pdcontentcomponentid=408193&pdmfid=1519360&pdisurlapi=true>
- Sondershaus, F. (2017). *Frühzeitige Öffentlichkeitsbeteiligung im Kontext der Windenergie. Von der Theorie in die Praxis* [Hintergrundpapier]. FA Wind. https://www.fachagentur-windenergie.de/fileadmin/files/Veroeffentlichungen/FA_Wind_fruehzeitige_Oeffentlichkeitsbeteiligung_Theorie_Praxis_2017-12.pdf
- SPD Brandenburg, CDU Brandenburh, & Bündnis 90/ Die Grünen Brandenburg. (2019). *Zusammenhalt, Nachhaltigkeit, Sicherheit – Ein neues Kapitel für Brandenburg. Gemeinsamer Koalitionsvertrag zwischen SPD Brandenburg, CDU Brandenburg und Bündnis90/ Die Grünen Brandenburg* [Koalitionsvertrag]. Landesregierung Brandenburg. https://www.brandenburg.de/media/bb1.a.3833.de/Koalitionsvertrag_Endfassung.pdf
- SPD, Bündnis 90/Die Grünen, & FDP. (2021). *Mehr Fortschritt wagen Bündnis für Freiheit, Gerechtigkeit und Nachhaltigkeit Koalitionsvertrag 2021 – 2025 zwischen der Sozialdemokratischen Partei Deutschlands (SPD), BÜNDNIS 90 / DIE GRÜNEN und den Freien Demokraten (FDP)* [Koalitionsvertrag]. <https://www.bundesregierung.de/breg-de/service/gesetzesvorhaben/koalitionsvertrag-2021-1990800>
- SPD-Fraktion, CDU-Fraktion, & Fraktion BÜNDNIS 90/DIE GRÜNEN. (2021). *Entschließungsantrag zu Gesetzentwurf der Landesregierung—Gesetz zur Regelung von Mindestabständen von Windenergieanlagen zu Wohngebäuden im Land Brandenburg (Brandenburgisches Windenergieanlagenabstandsgesetz—BbgWEAAbG) (Abtrag Drucksache 7/ 5546)*. Landtag Brandenburg. https://www.parlamentsdokumentation.brandenburg.de/starweb/LBB/ELVIS/parlادoku/w7/drs/ab_5500/5546.pdf
- Staatskanzlei Brandenburg. (2018). *Woidke im Bundesrat: Brandenburger Initiative für mehr Akzeptanz der Windkraft* [Pressemitteilung]. Land Brandenburg. <https://www.brandenburg.de/cms/detail.php/bb1.c.612185.de>
- Statistik der Kohlenwirtschaft e.V. (2023). *Beschäftigte im Braunkohlenbergbau nach Revieren* [dataset]. <https://kohlenstatistik.de/downloads/braunkohle/>
- Steffen, U. (2019, February 19). *Maßnahmenpaket der Landesregierung Brandenburg. Erneuerbare Energien und Bürgerinteressen im fairen Miteinander (6-Punkte-Plan)*.

3. Regionalkonferenz: Prignitz-Oberhavel (Neuruppin) am 19.02.2019 „Neue Chancen für Kommunen und Stadtwerke durch aktuelle Akzeptanzmaßnahmen bei den Erneuerbaren Energien“. https://www.prignitz-oberhavel.de/fileadmin/dateien/dokumente/REM/MWE_Regionalkonferenz_0219/02_Ma%C3%9Fnahmenpaket_Landesregierung.pdf
- Steyer, C.-D. (2010, August 13). Steuer auf Windräder: Luckau will die Verunstaltung der Landschaft verhindern. *Tagespiegel*. <https://www.tagesspiegel.de/potsdam/brandenburg/luckau-will-die-verunstaltung-der-landschaft-verhindern-6477454.html#:~:text=Mit%20einer%20deutschlandweit%20bislang%20einmaligen,parteilose%20B%C3%BCrgermeister%20Gerald%20Lehmann%20mit.>
- Süddeutsche Zeitung. (2018, September 3). Kabinett—Potsdam: Woidke stellt Windkraft-Initiative vor: Verband alarmiert. *Süddeutsche Zeitung*. <https://www.sueddeutsche.de/politik/kabinett-potsdam-woidke-stellt-windkraft-initiative-vor-verband-alarmiert-dpa.urn-newsml-dpa-com-20090101-180903-99-806511>
- Tagesschau online. (2022, March 8). Energie-Embargo gegen Moskau: Habeck warnt vor ‘schwersten’ Schäden. *Tagesschau Online*. <https://www.tagesschau.de/wirtschaft/energie/debatte-energieimporte-101.html>
- Tagesschau online. (2023, November 18). *Berlin Brandenburg: ‘In der Mittelschicht sind die Unterschiede zwischen Ost und West noch offensichtlich’*. <https://www.tagesschau.de/inland/regional/berlin/rbb-in-der-mittelschicht-sind-die-unterschiede-zwischen-ost-und-west-noch-offensichtlich-100.html#:~:text=Je%20nach%20Statistik%20sind%20die,Ostdeutschland%20hingegen%20nur%2052.000%20Euro.>
- Taz. (2009, May 15). Viel heiße Luft; Parlament Brandenburg geht ein bisschen auf Windkraftgegner zu. *Taz*. <https://advance.lexis.com/document?crd=b92f94c9-dcbc-4188-bc12-fb95c8de1163&pddocfullpath=%2Fshared%2Fdocument%2Fnews%2Furn%3AcontentItem%3A7VP4-CM91-2SDD-M04N-00000-00&pdsourcingtype=&pdcontentcomponentid=158474&pdmfid=1519360&pdisurlapi=true>
- Taz. (2018, November 6). Windrädern droht das Aus. *Taz*. <https://taz.de/Windraedern-droht-das-Aus/!5544471/>
- Vosges, J. (2003, April 10). Wind in der Flaute. *Taz*. <https://taz.de/Wind-in-der-Flaute/!790485/>
- Walker, B. (2022). A Territorial Perspective on Urban and Regional Energy Transitions: Shifting Power Densities in the Berlin-Brandenburg Region. *International Journal of Urban and Regional Research*, 46(5), 766–783. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1468-2427.13120>
- Wegner, N. (2022, July 21). *Wind-an-Land-Gesetz. Überblick und erste Einschätzungen zum WaLG*. Online-Seminar. <https://stiftung-umweltenergierecht.de/wp-content/uploads/2022/07/Was-steckt-im-Osterpaket-WaLG-2022-07-21-1.pdf>
- Wehrmann, B. (2023). *German onshore wind power. Output, business and perspectives*. [Factsheet]. Clean Energy Wire. <https://www.cleanenergywire.org/factsheets/german-onshore-wind-power-output-business-and-perspectives>
- Wolf, I. (2020). Soziales Nachhaltigkeitsbarometer der Energiewende 2019. Kernaussagen und Zusammenfassung der wesentlichen Ergebnisse. *IASS Brochure*. <https://doi.org/10.2312/IASS.2020.010>

- Wolf, I., Teune, S., Fischer, A.-K., & Huttarsch, J.-H. (2021). *Windausbau vor Ort – Potentiale erkennen, Beteiligung und Teilhabe stärken* [Pdf]. 15 pages. <https://doi.org/10.48481/IAS.2021.026>
- Zerzawy, F., Wettingfeld, M., & Grimm, F. (2023). *Akzeptanz durch Beteiligung von Kommunen und Bürger*innen: Wie finanzielle Anreize den Ausbau erneuerbarer Energien in Bayern voranbringen können* [Kurzstudie]. Forum Ökologisch-Soziale Marktwirtschaft. https://foes.de/publikationen/2023/2023-01_FOES_Kurzstudie_finanzielle_Beteiligung_EE.pdf

ANNEX 1: BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bibliography including the list of 58 documents consulted

Author name	Document name	Document type	Year
Agentur für Erneuerbare Energien (AEE)	Umfrage: Wunsch nach Versorgungssicherheit beflügelt Akzeptanz von Erneuerbaren Energien	Press Release	2022
Agora Energiewende	Understanding the Energiewende. FAQ on the ongoing transition of the German power system.	Report	2022
Berliner Zeitung	Die Schattenseite des Windkraft-Booms Windenergie hat Konjunktur. Doch Bürgerinitiativen und Gerichte machen die Suche nach neuen Standorten immer schwieriger.	Journal Article	2002
Bovet, Jana	Steuerung der Windenergie durch Raumordnung Aktuelle Rechtsprechung als Herausforderung für die Planung	Journal Article	2015
Bues, Andrea	Planning, Protest, and Contentious Politics	Journal Article	2019
Bunzel et al.	Hidden outlaws in the forest? A legal and spatial analysis of onshore wind energy in Germany	Journal Article	2019
Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz (BMWK)	Überblickspapier Osterpaket	Report	2022
BMWK	Das steckt im Osterpaket	Newsletter	2022
BWE	Windenergieausbau nicht ersticken – Privilegierung von Windenergieanlagen im Planungsrecht wichtig für Klimaschutz und Strukturwandel	Press release	2018
Bündnis für Bernau	Bernauer Erklärung gegen ungebremste Windkraftnutzung.	Website	2018
Colell et al.	Hintergrund: Konflikte und Akteure – Gesellschaftliche Herausforderungen bei der Umsetzung der Stromwende.	Journal Article	2022

Dohmen & Hornig	Die große Luftnummer	Newspaper Article	2004
Dubro, Lukas	Energiewende retten!	Newspaper Article	2014
Eichenauer, Eva	Im Gegenwind. Lokaler Widerstand gegen den Bau von Windkraftanlagen in Brandenburg. Ergebnisse einer Onlinebefragung.	Journal Article	2016
Eichenauer & Gailing	Gute Bedingungen für lokale Wertschöpfung aus Windkraftanlagen. Erfahrungen und Empfehlungen	Policy Paper	2020
Eichenauer et al.	Bürgerinitiativen gegen Windkraftanlagen und der Aufschwung rechtspopulistischer Bewegungen	Journal Article	2018
Ermisch et al.	Gemeinsam gewinnen – Windenergie vor Ort. Ein Grundlagenpapier zu den Themen Wertschöpfung, Bürgerbeteiligung und Akzeptanz	Report	2018
Fachagentur für Windenergie	Brandenburg (BB). Länderinformationen Zur Windenergie	Website	2023
Frese, Alfons	Wirtschaftsminister Christoffers im Interview: „Der Osten zahlt zu hohe Strompreise“	Newspaper Article	2013
Gläser, Heike	Boom trotz Unsicherheiten	Newspaper Article	1998
Greive et al.	Was die Länder gegen Gabriels Öko-Pläne aufbringt	Newspaper Article	2014
Hirschl et al.	Gutachten zum Klimaplan Brandenburg	Report	2023
Höppner & Anker	Windkraft: Mehr Einfluss und Informationen für Bürger	Newspaper Article	2019
International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), Global Wind Energy Council (GWEC)	30 Years of Policies for Wind Energy: Lessons from 12 Wind Energy Markets	Report	2013
KNE	Moratorium für die Genehmigung von Windenergieanlagen in	Position Paper	2019

	Brandenburg. "KNE-Wortmeldung"		
Kübler, Knut	Der lange Schatten des Energiekonzepts 2010 und die nächste Etappe der Energiewende	Journal Article	2013
Landesamt für Umwelt, Gesundheit und Verbraucherschutz Brandenburg (LUGV)	Bürgerbeteiligung an Planungs- und Genehmigungsverfahren für Windkraftanlagen	Leaflet	2012 (?)
Local Energy Consulting	Akzeptanz und lokale Teilhabe in der Energiewende. Handlungsempfehlungen für eine umfassende Akzeptanzpolitik	Report	2020
Neller, Marc	Gegen den Wind	Newspaper Article	2012
Metzner, Thorsten	Ausblick: Was Brandenburg im Jahr 2012 erwartet	Newspaper Article	2012
Ministerium für Infrastruktur und Landesplanung (MIL)	Windkraftausbau in Brandenburg kommt voran: Neues Flächenzielgesetz in Kraft	Press Release	2023
Ministerium für Ländliche Entwicklung, Umwelt und Landwirtschaft des Landes Brandenburg (MLUK)	Klimaplan Brandenburg	Action programme	2023
Ministerium für Ländliche Entwicklung, Umwelt und Verbraucherschutz des Landes Brandenburg (MLUV)	Landespolitischer Maßnahmenkatalog zum Klimaschutz und zur Anpassung an die Folgen des Klimawandels	Catalog/ Brochure	2008
Ministerium für Wirtschaft, Arbeit und Energie (MWAE)	Energiestrategie 2040	Report	2022

Ministerium für Wirtschaft, Arbeit und Energie (MWAE)	Land verstärkt Beratung zu erneuerbaren Energien	Newspaper Article	2019
Ministerium für Wirtschaft, Arbeit und Energie (MWAE)	Bevölkerung stärker in die Energiewende einbeziehen	Press release	2018
Müller, & Morton	Brandenburg-Report: Zum Stand der Windenergieerzeugung in Brandenburg	Report	2021
Müller, & Morton	Briefing Report: Wind and Solar Projects in Brandenburg	Journal Article	2021
Müller, & Morton	The space, the time, and the money. Wind energy politics in East Germany	Journal Article	2021
NABU Brandenburg, & BUND Brandenburg	Gemeinsame Position von NABU und BUND Brandenburg zur Windkraftnutzung.	Position Paper	2016
Nowakowski, Gerd	Brandenburg: Windkraft? Nein danke!	Newspaper Article/ Opinion Piece	2008
Osberghaus, Henno	Was schert mich mein Wind von gestern	Newspaper Article	1996
Overwien & Groenerwald	Viel Wind um den Wind. Aktuelle Herausforderungen für die Regionalplanung in Brandenburg	Journal Article	2015
Rada, Uwe	In Potsdam weht ein scharfer Wind	Newspaper Article	2008
Rettet die Uckermark (RdU)	Wir an Sie	Website	N.d.
Reusswig et al.	Energiekonflikte. Akzeptanzkriterien und Gerechtigkeitsvorstellungen in der Energiewende. Kerneergebnisse und Handlungsempfehlungen eines interdisziplinären Forschungsprojektes	Journal Article	2016 a
Reusswig et al.	Against the wind: Local opposition to the German Energiewende.	Journal Article	2016 b
Salecki et al.	Finanzielle Beteiligung von betroffenen Kommunen bei	Report	2020

	Planung, Bau und Betrieb von erneuerbaren Energieanlagen (FinBEE). Ergebnisse für die Windenergie		
Schafmeister, Christian	Braunkohle in Sachsen-Anhalt: Ungeliebt und doch gebraucht	Newspaper Article	2014
Sondershaus, Frank	Frühzeitige Öffentlichkeitsbeteiligung im Kontext der Windenergie. Von der Theorie in die Praxis	Report	2017
SPD Brandenburg, CDU Brandenburg, & Bündnis 90/ Die Grünen Brandenburg	Zusammenhalt, Nachhaltigkeit, Sicherheit – Ein neues Kapitel für Brandenburg. Gemeinsamer Koalitionsvertrag zwischen SPD Brandenburg, CDU Brandenburg und Bündnis90/ Die Grünen Brandenburg	Coalition agreement	2019
SPD, Bündnis 90/Die Grünen, & FDP	Mehr Fortschritt wagen Bündnis für Freiheit, Gerechtigkeit und Nachhaltigkeit Koalitionsvertrag 2021 – 2025 zwischen der Sozialdemokratischen Partei Deutschlands (SPD), BÜNDNIS 90 / DIE GRÜNEN und den Freien Demokraten (FDP)	Coalition agreement	2021
Steffen, Uwe	Maßnahmenpaket der Landesregierung Brandenburg. Erneuerbare Energien und Bürgerinteressen im fairen Miteinander (6-Punkte-Plan	Report	2019
Steyer, Claus-Dieter	Steuer auf Windräder: Luckau will die Verunstaltung der Landschaft verhindern	Newspaper Article	2010
Staatskanzlei Brandenburg	Woidke im Bundesrat: Brandenburger Initiative für mehr Akzeptanz der Windkraft	Press Release	2018
Süddeutsche Zeitung	Woidke stellt Windkraft-Initiative vor: Verband alarmiert	Newspaper Article	2018
Voges, Jürgen	Wind in der Flaute	Newspaper Article	2003
Wolf, Dr. Ingo	Soziales Nachhaltigkeitsbarometer der Energiewende 2019. Kernaussagen und	Report	2020

	Zusammenfassung der wesentlichen Ergebnisse		
Wolf et al.	Windausbau vor Ort – Potentiale erkennen, Beteiligung und Teilhabe stärken	Journal Article	2021

ANNEX 2: INTERVIEWEES

List of interviewees (including role of interviewee, date, duration of the interview);

Interviews	Role of interviewee	Date	Setting	Duration
Interview 1	Politician in the Brandenburg state parliament	05/09/2023	Face-to-face	60 min
Interview 2	Official in the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Energy of the federal state of Brandenburg	19/09/2023	Online	45 min
Interview 3	Expert from regional planning in Brandenburg	06/09/2023	Face-to-face	80 min
Interview 4	Mayor of a municipality in Brandenburg	04/09/2023	Online	60 min
Interview 5	Mayor of a municipality in Brandenburg	21/09/2023	Online	70 min
Interview 6	Two employees from an energy company in Brandenburg	24/07/2023	Online, group-interview	90 min
Interview 7	Expert in renewable energy expansion from the scientific field	23/03/2023	Online	60 min
Interview 8	Expert in renewable energy and participation from the scientific field	09/01/2023	Online	60 min

ANNEX 3: MEETINGS AND EVENTS ATTENDED

As part of the empirical work, we have joined two online events about wind energy. The first event took place on 20.06.22 and was called 'It needs to become faster?! Expansion of renewables – What are the key issues for practitioners. The second event took place on 30.03.23 and was called 'The energy transition in municipalities: Interlinkages between regional value creation, local acceptance and financial participation'. We took notes during these events and gained access to the slides that were presented.